

AGEMERA

Critical Raw Materials for
a Resilient Europe

DELIVERABLE 4.5
APPLICATION VALIDATION REPORT

Comparative validation of applications developed by mapping with
results of seismic profiling, geological profiles and numerical calculations

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Executive Summary

In the case of conducting research at great depths, where geological knowledge is limited, new passive methods of spatial rock mass profiling may be ambiguous from the point of view of the reliability of the results. It is therefore important to attempt to verify the results of innovative methods indirectly based on other, currently used monitoring systems and available geological data. Considering the great depth of deposits in KGHM mines, it can be stated that, of all passive monitoring methods developed within the AGEMERA project, may bring significant improvement in terms of preliminary exploration or evaluation of rockmass condition. Muography seems to be the most suitable method for long-term spatial monitoring of deposit conditions and geomechanical hazards distribution with the progress of mining works.

Comparison of results from different types of monitoring systems would enable point-by-point verification of the results, based on attempts to find correlations between individual parameters.

Additionally, based on previous achievements in geomechanical analyses, it can be noted that it is theoretically possible to use spatial numerical simulations for direct verification of spatial monitoring systems for passive measurements developed within the AGEMERA project. However, for the comparison to be reliable, it is necessary to first carry out a detailed validation of the numerical model based on underground measurements, considering the passage of time, to represent the behaviour of the rock mass with the advancing mining works.

The task will focus on detailed evaluation of data obtained with various sensing methods, and processing done with applications from T4.4 (including 3D muon-based density measurements), by the comparative validation with data from current state-of-the-art mining monitoring systems and 4D numerical simulations (including the progress of mining works in time). The analysis was prepared for the two use cases. The first use case focused on the analysis of the possibility of geomechanical hazard assessment with the use of **muon imaging**. As usual, the studies started with **muon radiography (2D) mode**, which is the standard and only way to start muon imaging campaigns. The second use case aimed to determine if **muon tomography (3D) imaging mode** could be realised in a deep mine setting with a minimal number of measurement positions. On a grand scale, the survey was targeted to test if muon imaging could be a suitable solution as a remote sensing exploration tool and for profiling structural geological faults at great depths.

Results of analyses were exported to the OPT/NET database, which allowed us to:

1. Validation of method usefulness from the perspective of underground mining.
2. Spatial comparison of results from different monitoring systems.
3. Assessing muon imaging constraints.
4. Improving detector design and capabilities for high temperatures and extreme humidities.

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List of Acronyms

Abbreviation	Full Form	Description
AB	Advisory Board	Project advisory body
AGEMERA	Agile Exploration and Geo-Modelling for European Critical Raw Materials	Project title
AI	Artificial Intelligence	Intelligent data processing system
AIKP	AI Knowledge Pack	AI-based analytical tool or module
CANG	Convergence by means of ANGular Sensors	Tunnel convergence monitoring system
CDC	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention	US health authority cited in references
CO	Carbon Monoxide	Toxic underground gas
COG	Cloud-Optimized GeoTIFF	Format for geospatial raster data
CRM	Critical Raw Materials	Essential raw materials for EU economy
CSAMT	Controlled-Source Audio-frequency Magnetotellurics	Electromagnetic geophysical method
CSIC	Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas	Spanish scientific institution
CSIRO	Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation	Australian research agency (for HI-D Cells)
CUPRUM	KGHM CUPRUM sp. z o.o. - CBR	Polish R&D centre involved in project
DPF	Diesel Particulate Filter	Emission control device in diesel engines
EC	European Commission	Executive body of the European Union
EGF	Empirical Green's Function	Seismic interferometry concept
EPISODES	–	Seismic platform/database used in the project
ERP	Electrical Resistivity Profiling	Geophysical method
ERT	Electrical Resistivity Tomography	Subsurface imaging method
EU	European Union	Funding organization
FBG	Fiber Bragg Grating	Optical sensing technology
FEM	Finite Element Method	Numerical modelling method
FRAME	Forecasting and Assessing Europe's Strategic Raw Materials Needs	EU-funded project
GHB	Generalized Hoek-Brown	Rock mass strength model
GPR	Ground Penetrating Radar	Geophysical imaging method
GPS	Global Positioning System	Satellite positioning system
GSI	Geological Strength Index	Rock quality classification
GTS NX	Geo-Technical Software NX	3D FEM modelling software
GUI	Graphical User Interface	Web platform for visual data analysis
HI-D	Hollow Inclusion – Deep	Rock stress cell technology
IP	Induced Polarization	Geophysical method for subsurface imaging
KDI	Key Deposit Indicator	Criterion for mining method selection
KGHM	KGHM Polska Miedź S.A.	Polish copper mining company
KMI	Key Mining Indicator	Criterion for selecting mining method
LGCB	Legnica–Głogów Copper Basin	Mining region in Poland

LGCD	Legnica–Głogów Copper District	Same as above – broader geological term
LITH	Lithica	Project partner in passive seismic
MEMS	Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems	Miniature sensing technology
MLS	Mobile Laser Scanning	Method of spatial data collection
MSHA	Mine Safety and Health Administration	U.S. mining safety authority
NIOSH	National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health	U.S. agency for occupational safety
NSB	North Sudetic Basin	Geological region in SW Poland
NSW	New South Wales	Australian state – cited in mining codes
OPT/NET	OPT/NET BV	Partner responsible for the web platform
PMPTL / PMTPL	–	Commercial extensometer brand cited in references
PPE	Personal Protective Equipment	Safety gear
RFRI	Roof Fall Risk Index	Hazard assessment tool for stone mines
RQD	Rock Quality Designation	Rock mass characterization index
RCI	Rock Core Index	Rock quality indicator
REE	Rare Earth Elements	Strategic elements for technology and defence
SF	Safety Factor	Geotechnical stability indicator
SI	Seismic Interferometry	Passive seismic processing technique
SIMS	Sustainable Intelligent Mining Systems	Related EU project
TLS	Terrestrial Laser Scanning	Stationary 3D scanning method
TOPSIS	Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution	MCDM decision-making method
TSF	Tailings Storage Facility	Waste containment area in mining
TZ	Translation Zone	Layer designation in numerical models
UCS	Uniaxial Compressive Strength	Key rock strength parameter
UBC	University of British Columbia	Referenced in mining method classification
WHS	Work Health and Safety	Occupational standards for mines
WUG	Wyższy Urząd Górniczy (in Polish)	Polish State Mining Authority

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1. Introduction

1.1. Sustainable Extraction of CRM at Large Depths

Maintaining European industry at a high level of innovation and development of modern technology, which is aimed at a responsible and sustainable economy, requires access to the CRM. The last decades of world history have shown that reliable access to crucial raw materials, which is a pivotal part of the supply chain, can be easily disrupted. It causes not only financial losses for industries but can also disrupt crucial parts of European economies, e.g. power supply, health, and transport. Therefore, the EU introduced a special policy (Critical Raw Materials Act) to secure the European market in this field (EC, 2018; 2024). Importance of this issue can be seen in the lists of CRMs, which have been updated many times in recent years (Zhang et al., 2023; Moore, et al., 2024). Lists of CRMs in selected years is presented in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1. Modifications of the CRM list in selected years (EU, 2024)

2011	2017	2023
Antimony Beryllium Cobalt Fluorspar Gallium Germanium Graphite Indium Magnesium Niobium PGMs REEs Tantalum Tungsten	Antimony Baryte Beryllium Bismuth Borat Cobalt Coking coal Fluorspar Gallium Germanium Hafnium Helium Indium Magnesium Natural graphite Natural rubber Niobium	Antimony Arsenic Baryte Bauxite Beryllium Bismuth Borat Cobalt Coking coal Copper Feldspar Fluorspar Phosphorus Scandium Silicon metal Tantalum Tungsten Vanadium PGMs* HREEs* LREEs*

* PGMs – Platinum Group Metals; HREEs – Heavy Rare Earth Elements;
LREEs – Light Rare Earth Elements

As can be seen in the list of CRMs, which has expanded in recent years, CRMs are crucial to the European market; hence, there is a strong need to find and protect reliable and lasting access to these materials. This aspect is a meaningful part of sustainability and circular economy, prioritised in EU. It is one of the pivotal issues for EU to become a climate-neutral continent by 2050 (Tomala & Urbaniec, 2024). Looking into recent years, notably the last decade, many hard-to-predict events took place e.g. pandemic, military conflicts and other geopolitical issues, which had a significant influence on the global supply chains, including critical raw materials. To have in mind that CRMs are key elements for both civilian and defence industries brings about serious concerns in Europe. To mitigate this issue, local extraction of crucial materials is needed. It seems to be a necessity despite social resistance against mining industry projects (van As, 2021;

Dino & Cavallo, 2022; Umbach, 2024). According to Euromines-Manifest (Euromines, 2024) there are 3 ways to make stronger European raw materials supply chain system. As can be seen in Figure 1.1, meaningful part of the Enabling and Maintaining is innovating process in operational efficiency.

ENABLING AND MAINTAINING <i>License to operate</i>	GROWING AND INVESTING <i>A competitive framework</i>	BEING RESPONSIBLE <i>Recognising operational, ESG excellence</i>
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Unlocking exploration potential	<input type="checkbox"/> Conditions for growth in regulatory trends	<input type="checkbox"/> Fostering societal dialogue and public acceptance
<input type="checkbox"/> Maintaining and multiplying mining operations	<input type="checkbox"/> Policies focused on operational expenditures	<input type="checkbox"/> Recognising EU frontrunner status and cost importing lower ESG
<input type="checkbox"/> Balancing regulatory permitting conditions throughout mine life cycle	<input type="checkbox"/> EU monitoring and reacting to international competition	<input type="checkbox"/> Amplifying market opportunities for Europe's, ESG driven industry
<input type="checkbox"/> Innovating operational efficiency		

Figure 1.1. Three ways for a stronger European raw materials supply (Euromines, 2024)

Awareness of this serious issue in some European countries lead to deeper research of known raw material resources e.g. in Nordic countries (Boyd & Gautneb, 2016; Jonsson et al., 2022), Poland (Nieć et al., 2014), Greece (Gamaletsos et al., 2019). Thanks to these European countries' activities and cooperation EU (EC, 2018) determined all known resources of CMRs, which can be seen in Figure 1.2.

Figure 1.2. CRMs deposits in Europe (EuroGeoSurveys, 2024)

There were also other EU projects which were focused on the different facets regarding raw material potential in Europe like GeoERA, FRAME and MINDeSEA (FRAME, 2024;

GeoERA, 2024; Wittenberg & Oliveira, 2023). Many of determined deposits might be successfully exploited by means of underground mining technology. Some activities aimed to stimulation the mining industry were implemented in 2010 as ProMine project which was co-funded by EU (Bertrand et al., 2016). In 2022 European Federation of Geologists prepared list of 10 mining opportunities in EU for critical minerals, 5 of them have to be exploited using underground mining methods (Eurogeologist, 2022). List of these deposits is presented in Table 1.2.

Table 1.2. List of promising CRMs deposits in Europe (acc. Eurogeologist, 2022)

Country	Project	Commodity
Portugal	Lagoa Salgada	Zink, Lead, Copper
Czech Republic	Cinovec	Lithium, Tin
Finland	Sakatti	Copper, Nickel, PGEs
Greece	Skouries	Copper, Gold
Spain	Masa Valverde	Zink, Lead, Copper
Spain	San Jose	Lithium

These projects are in different stages of research or/and investment process. To meet future challenges in many different aspects in the field of raw material extraction process, there is a need for the development of mining technologies. This development process is necessary to ensure a proper safety level, cost-efficiency and environmental protection. There is a common knowledge that currently, in most cases, shallow and easily reachable deposits are unavailable (for different reasons) or have been mined out, hence underground exploitation of deep deposits is the only one option (van As, 2021). Looking into the current mining industry and future mining trends, extraction is becoming more problematic due to deeper exploitation and more difficult geological conditions; therefore, progress in new mining technology is crucial to fulfil the requirements for a sustainable mining process. In most cases, one of the distinctive features of CRMs deposits is their low grade; hence, economically and technically justified extraction must cover significant numbers of ore tonnes. It should also be kept in mind that fulfilling the requirements of sustainable underground mining should balance between economic viability and social and environmental impact.

There are many different underground mining methods that can be utilised for deposit extraction. Simplified lists of mining methods, with four main groups of methods, are listed in Table 1.3.

Table 1.3. Simplified list of underground mining methods (Atlas Copco, 2007)

Mining method	Type of deposit
Sublevel stopping (Figure 1.3)	Orebodies with steep inclination angle, stable rock around orebody, competent ore with regular shape
Sublevel caving (Figure 1.4)	Orebodies with steep inclination angle, footwall drifts stable, ore with regular shape, orebody and host rock strength parameters ensure fracture under control.
Room-and-pillar (Figure 1.5)	Small inclination or flat deposits with limited thickness
Long wall (Figure 1.6)	Thin, bedded deposit, large horizontal extension

Figure 1.3. Sublevel stopping mining method layout (acc. Atlas Copco, 2007)

Figure 1.4. Sublevel caving mining method layout (acc. Atlas Copco, 2007)

Figure 1.5. Room-and-pillar mining method layout (acc. Atlas Copco, 2007)

Figure 1.6. Longwall mining method layout

Real mining and geological conditions are often more complicated, therefore abovementioned methods are often modified and combined to optimise the mining process (Mousavi & Sellers, 2019). For example, the sublevel caving method was normally applied to shallow deposits as the transition of exploitation from open pit to underground mines, however, this method was tailored to the much deeper deposits. This method was called block and panel caving and can be applied to the orebody placed above 1 km depth (Pierce, 2018; van As, 2021). One of the distinctive features of the block caving method is relatively low exploitation cost, however, it requires large capital investment to prepare the required infrastructure before exploiting a single tone of ore. For this reason, there is a visible trend to expand block height much above 250 – 300 m to optimise mining cost, although it relates to serious geomechanical challenges. In 2018, there were more than 50 active and considered cave mining projects in the world (van As, 2021).

Safe and profitable mining operations depend on the proper selection of the mining method. There are many indicators that should be taken into consideration and methods to select the most suitable mining method for the given deposit (Nieto, 2010; Ali & Kim, 2021; Mijalkovski et al., 2021). According to Nieto (2010) these indicators can be divided into two groups, namely:

- Key Ore Deposit Indicators (KDIs),
- Key Mining Method Indicators (KMIs).

KDIs are defined by internal qualities of the considered orebody and are fixed, as a result, cannot be changed or modified. A list of indicators for both groups is presented in Table 1.4.

Table 1.4. List of indicators considered during mining method selection

Indicators of mining selection	
Key Ore Deposit Indicators (KDIs)	Key Mining Method Indicators (KMIs)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • depth of deposit • ore strength • strength of host rock mass • shape and size of deposit • dip of orebody • ore grade • geological structure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • operating cost • development time • investment cost • rate of production • mechanisation • safety aspects • environmental impact • selectivity and flexibility

Complexity of the natural orebodies in different locations implies that each of mine has its own specific and it is very hard to copy some solution from one site to another without any changes.

1.2. Risks in Underground Mining

Industrial activity is inherently connected with risk, hence this aspect must be considered and managed very carefully throughout the whole lifecycle beginning from assumptions, design till decommissioning process and reclamation. Different types of hazards that can relate to industrial sectors determined their risk level. As other businesses mining companies are aimed to operate in efficient and profitable way but above all in safe manner (Badri et al., 2012).

Looking into underground mining enterprises there are much more challenges in the field of safety facets than in most other industry sectors because of specific working environment. It is not without reason that mining is perceived as one of the most hazardous industrial sectors (Iannacchione et al., 2007; Tripathy & Ala, 2018; Mining hazards, 2024), however it should be kept in mind that facts show that the most dangerous sector in EU is construction industry (EC, 2022). Working place located in underground space creates many specific threats containing ergonomic, physical and chemical (Baghaei & Badri, 2024) which is result of complex and often complicated mining operations that must be done to exploit ore (Löow & Nygren, 2019). We must be

aware that many of hazards encountered in underground mines aren't present in the traditional surface industry and incorporate the following threats:

- ground control issues (workings are surrounded by rocks),
- seismic activity,
- occurrence of harmful gases,
- ventilation issues (oxygen content, temperature, humidity, dust etc.),
- radiation,
- fire hazard (underground fire is much more dangerous),
- water hazard,
- seismic activity,
- bad visibility (lack of sunlight),
- vertical open spaces,
- moving vehicles and machines,
- others.

On the other hand, there are typical hazards like: energy related (electrical, chemical, mechanical), heavy mobile vehicles and equipment, uneven floor, poor visibility, muddy terrain etc. All these hazards are often associated with each other and create very dangerous and dynamic environment that is changing in continuous manner. From general perspective hazards associated with mining activity can be categorised as proposed by Naeini & Badri (2023) (Table 1.5).

Table 1.5. Categorisation of hazards

Hazards categorisation		
Hazards category	Agent	Hazard source
Chemical agents	Dust, silica, mercury, methane, smoke, carbon dioxide, etc.	Blasting, diesel motors, orebody, extraction processes, welding, spraying, grinding
Physical agents	Noise, heat stress, lighting	Blasting, drilling, hammering, environment
Biological	Infections	Environment, dampness, co-workers
Ergonomic	Difficult working position (bending, handling), carrying heavy loads, repetitive actions	Work method, tasks, tools
Accidents	Fire, falls, rock falls, slipping, flooding, hitting by machinery, electrocution, coughing by rotating/moving parts, trapping	Combustive materials, electric equipment, machines, water ingress

1.2.1. Ground Instability

From all abovementioned hazards one of the most dangerous is ground instability, which causes the most serious and fatal accidents in underground mines. We have to be aware that in underground mines we are in limited volume of open space surrounded by rocks hence unplanned and uncontrolled movement of rock is very serious danger for workers in area affected by this phenomenon (Code of practice, 2019). Ground failure

mechanisms can be divided into two types: gravity and rockburst. In the first type of mechanism discontinuities within a rockmass allowing to move fragments of rockmass into open spaces in form of rockfall from the roof or sidewall. Discontinuities can be a part natural rockmass structure (joints, faults, bedding planes) or might be result of mining-induced stress fractures and/or blasting related cracks). Rockburst phenomenon involves sudden rock breaking with dynamic movement of the rock into open space caused by release of elastic energy stored into rockmass (Ground control, 2024). Rockburst might also be triggered by seismic events. Stability of the rockmass in surrounding workings is result of many factors like mining method, geometry of workings, geological structure of the rockmass, mine out area, mining-induced stress. It should also be emphasized that instability of ground can affect mining infrastructure like workings, machines, transportation drifts, conveyors belts etc. and therefore disturb exploitation process.

Due to crucial importance of ground stability to the safety and productivity of mines constant process of risk assessment of instability hazard has to be established as a part of effective ground control management system. According to Code of practice (2019) related to the ground control provided by Government of Western Australia, Department of Mines, Industry Regulation and Safety the following key elements should be implemented into system (Figure 1.7).

Figure 1.7. Elements of effective ground control management system (Code of practice, 2019)

It is obvious that underground exploitation which relates to creation of empty spaces with different volume, shapes and functions like drifts, workings, chambers, and shafts changes stresses in surrounded rockmass and in some cases can cause instability of some parts of rockmass. Assessment of this hazard and mitigation of this threat is crucial to ensure proper level of safety. This process should include identification of zones in

the rockmass where instability might occur from different reasons e.g. (Code of practice, 2016; Ground control, 2024):

- increasing of stress in the rockmass due to expected changes in workings structure (including mineout area),
- presence of problematic geologic structures (faults, cracks, weak zones, etc.),
- improper type of ground support,
- deeper exploitation level,
- natural or mining induced seismicity,
- ground water,
- deteriorated ground support,
- unsuitable design of ground support,
- blast overbreaking,
- pillar collapse,
- other.

Ground control issues in surficial understanding are focused on roof control, however considering the geomechanical mechanism of ground control has to also incorporate aspects connected with mined out zone, floor control, pillar geometry, subsidence etc. (Peng, 2015; Moss & Kaiser, 2021). From the general perspective there are three main issues that must be investigated, namely: stress distribution, geological structure and seismic activity. In the last decade modern methods of numerical modelling have often applied to assess or predict stress distribution in the rockmass and help to indicate areas that could be prone to instability (Pytel et al., 2019; Fuławka et al., 2024). Understanding of threat types and their level is pivotal issue to provide suitable and effective ground control which includes: selection of mining method, excavation technique (e.g. mechanical, blasting), ground support (e.g. rock bolts, mesh, shotcrete etc.), backfilling, exploitation sequence, scaling, work organisation (Code of practice, 2019). Due to some level of uncertainty associated with all processes occurring in orebody monitoring systems must be also implemented to yield reliable data of real rockmass behaviour e.g. seismic monitors, convergence, stress monitors, etc. It is impossible to recognise rockmass in details, including geologic structure and rock parameters, therefore awareness of some level of uncertainties must be taken into consideration.

1.2.2. Water Hazard

Another serious hazard that must be considered and managed in underground mines is uncontrolled inrush water into workings that can create serious risk for workers and underground facilities. It is very important to recognize in detail location and number of aquifers, potential hydraulic connections and isolated water reservoirs that can inrush into mine. Danger inrush can also occur when any fluidized material suddenly inflows into open space causing dangerous situations for workers and mine infrastructure (Water management, 2024). It must be taken into consideration that some materials can be fluidized as a result of vibrations caused by seismic events (natural or mining induced), blasting, machines or other means (NSW code of practice, 2015). Assessment

of the water hazard must also cover dewatering process and other issues where significant amount of water is used in mining processes.

According to Bukowski (2015), three main kinds of water sources can be indicated:

- surrounding rock mass,
- surface water reservoirs,
- technological processes.

To ensure safety of underground mine operator has to assess the hazard regarding inundation and implement suitable solutions to control it. To control water hazard proper recognition of water sources must be conducted and suitable underground dewatering system must be employed. This kind of system consists mainly the following elements:

- pumps, with proper capacity,
- pipes,
- drain holes and lines,
- water dams and storages,
- control systems with monitoring.

Dewatering system and its parameters have to be tailored to the normal water inflow with additional capacity reserve in case of increased inflow, caused by some unpredictable events. It is reasonably impossible to recognise exact structure of water aquifers and reservoirs as well as weather and external inflows, hence reserve of capacity is needed. In some cases, amount of water which rushes into workings can be limited by sealing the connection between aquifer and the drifts by injection into the rock, special sealing material that fills the cracks and blocks or reduces water flow. Another preventive action that can be taken to avoid water hazard is dewatering water reservoirs or preparing water storages at the deepest level of the mine. Similar to the other types of hazard mine water has to be monitored to cover the following data: volume of water inflow, level of water is specified locations, chemical composition, parameters of pumping system (Guideline for Inrush, 2007). Measurement of aquifers is conducted by means of piezometers which are placed in boreholes conducted from surface. Systems of piezometers deliver the data of water level and monitor inflow rate if there is hydraulic connection between aquifers and underground tunnels.

Information about amount of water that inflows to the mine is estimated based on volume of water pumped from the mine and observation of the water level in water reservoirs in the underground dewatering system.

It should be taken into account that flowing water can be polluted and consists of many contaminants including gases, hence quality of underground water should also be monitored to protect people, environment and infrastructure from hazard. Water should be analysed to determine physical and chemical parameters which assess pollution level and help to adjust water purification system. Quality monitoring systems should be

tailored to the site conditions and incorporate detailed procedures for the analysis i.e. sample taking, sample preservation and handling; analytical methods used etc. (Schoeman, 2012).

1.2.3. Ventilation and Airborne Hazards

Underground mining is inherently connected with working in limited space with lack of natural ventilation, therefore first of all the most important issue is to ensure breathable air. It must be performed by means of ventilation system which is able to deliver in reliable manner appropriate amount of fresh air to guarantee acceptable working condition. It means that capability of the system provides proper oxygen level, remove and dilutes contamination, keep thermal comfort etc. It should be noted that the atmosphere in underground mines is a mixture of fresh air, gases emanating from surrounding rock mass, machines, mining process (e.g. blasting) and fires. Gases that can be present in underground mines may create hazards for workers because can be toxic, explosive or asphyxiating. In many cases dangerous gases are invisible and odourless (carbon dioxide and monoxide). It means that workers could be at serious risk related to the underground atmosphere therefore suitable risk assessment must be performed.

As a part of assessment proper geological recognition must be carried out which should indicate areas with gas emission hazard with determination of type and volume of gases. The following natural gases can be present in underground spaces (Brake, 2015; Airborne hazard, 2024):

- hydrogen sulphide (H₂S),
- methane (CH₄),
- carbon dioxide and monoxide (CO₂, CO),
- radon.

Other sources of toxic agents in the underground facilities can be mining processes and operations (i.e. fumes from diesel engines, blasting operations, dust, welding, grinding etc.). These agents incorporated:

- sulphur dioxide (SO₂),
- nitrogen oxides (NO_x),
- ammonia (NH₃),
- dust and silica,
- isocyanates (sealing agents, resin),
- refrigerants (air conditioning systems),
- other.

Apart from toxic hazard, serious hazard associated with ventilation is unbreathable atmosphere occurrence, caused by:

- oxygen deficiency,
- fires,

- concentrations of gases in the working place atmosphere above acceptable limits,
- gases eruption from natural reservoirs (e.g. methane, carbon dioxide),
- combustive gases explosion or coal dust explosion,
- confined space without proper fresh air diffusion (lack or insufficient airflow).

Airborne hazards can also incorporate dangerous dust, aerosol or vapours. Exposure to the hazardous agents (gases, vapours and aerosols) can cause health problems, occupational illness or death (Airborne hazard, 2024). Harmful agents which consist toxic gases, diesel particles, mineral particles, may have negative impact on the health in the form of nausea, asthma, eye or skin irritation, cancers, intoxication etc. Many different strategies and technologies might be applied to control and limit exposure of workers to the hazardous substances (CDC, 2024). One of the major sources of dangerous gases (CO, CO₂, NO_x, SO₂ and hydrocarbons) in many underground mines are diesel engines. In this case there are three main ways to reduce or eliminate this threat, namely:

- development of diesel engines,
- ventilation systems,
- electric machines,
- redesign of processes.

In the last decades there has been constant development of diesel engine to improve working parameters, efficiency, and reduction of fumes. There were implemented many solutions in injection system, filters (diesel particulate filter (DPF)) and control systems (CDC Report, 2012), however it seems that further development of this technology is reasonably impractical. There is visible trend towards development of electric equipment to replace diesel engine. In the meantime, reduction of exposure to diesel fumes is done on the basis of applying modern types of diesel engines, improving ventilation systems and separation workers from dangerous agents (PPE, enclosed cabins).

In example limitation of the emission gases from rock mass can be achieved by using an efficient draining system that removes gases from the rock mass. These kinds of systems consist of draining holes, pipes, and fans. Other methods that are also possible to utilize include the sealing or closing of dangerous areas by using sealing agents, which are injected into the rock mass, or barriers (dams, pillars, plugs).

1.2.4. Mobile Equipment Hazards

Statistics show that interactions with machines are also one the main causes of injuries in mining sector (Sanmiquel et al., 2018, Sunmiquel et al., 2024, MSHA, 2024; Identec solution, 2024). Mining industry utilizes many types of different mobile equipment including vehicles, transportation systems (e.g. conveyor belts, lifts), processing equipment (pumps, compressors etc.). Increased level of this kind of threat is connected mainly with specific underground environment which is often characterized as limited

and dark space, where it is hard to see obstacles and workers, in results these uncomfortable conditions have impact on safety and still many accidents happen. Environment factor is also connected with rapid progress of mechanization which helps to optimize extractive process and makes mining processes more efficient; however, it triggers risk connected with large number of equipment is used in limited space which increases risk level despite implementation of safety procedures and solutions (Sakinala et al., 2024).

Hazard related to the mobile equipment included (Mining hazards, 2024):

- falling off mobile vehicles or equipment (during transport, maintenance activity),
- being crushed by machinery (e.g. crusher),
- being caught in between equipment and machinery (gears, conveyor belts, etc.),
- being struck by machines or equipment,
- being run over by machines,
- collision between vehicles,
- collision between vehicle and fixed object or structure (e.g. sidewall, element of infrastructure),
- driving into vertical open spaces (shafts, chambers).

In these kinds of accidents workers injuries are often very serious including fatalities. These sorts of accidents occur not only due to poor visibility and limited space, but also because inadequate separation, loss of control, poor traffic management, use equipment in poor condition or damaged, organisation issues and so on.

1.2.5. Other Hazards

It is obvious that underground mining is not free from typical group of hazards that are present in almost every branch of industry. In this group, then can be called in general, workplace hazards are:

- physical treats (like noise, vibration, heat, electricity etc.),
- chemical hazards (exposure for toxic substances),
- ergonomic (uncomfortable working position, carrying heavy loads, long repetitive activity,
- biological hazards (infections),
- socio-economical threats (stress, trauma),
- organisational threats.

All these facets also have to be assessed in a proper way to create functional, effective and comprehensive safety systems, which limit risk to people in the workplace. It is also important that these kinds of systems should be reviewed and updated in a frequent way.

1.2.6. Accidents in Underground Mines

As a background of accidents in mining industry is good to see across whole mining sector. According to Report Linker (2025), in 2023 in selected European countries fatal accidents related to mining and quarrying were equal 46. Detailed data can be seen in Figure 1.8.

Figure 1.8. Fatal accidents in mining sector in 2023 (acc. ReportLinker, 2025)

As can be seen from chart, top of the list is occupied by Poland, what was related to accidents in underground coal mines (10 fatalities), one of the accidents caused 4 fatalities. In this case 4 workers were deadly hit by pipe from backfill system. Data about fatalities in mining industry in selected European countries and US from last decade is presented in Table 1.6.

Table 1.6. Fatalities number in selected countries (ReportLinker, 2025)

Year	Number of fatalities				
	US	Poland	Spain	Norway	France
2010	71	26	7	0	4
2011	37	29	11	2	3
2012	35	27	3	0	3
2013	41	18	9	7	0
2014	43	25	5	0	0
2015	26	16	8	2	1
2016	24	27	3	13	2
2017	27	11	2	1	7
2018	27	18	7	1	5
2019	27	19	1	1	4
2020	29	14	4	0	5
2021	37	11	6	0	2
2022	29	15	4	3	4
2023		15	4	4	4

Observing underground mining sector, large number of fatalities in Poland is related mainly to the size of underground mining sector (there are still about 90,000 employees) and their structure (most of employees work in relatively deep underground coal miners). However, looking deeply at the accidents factor, situation looks differently. For example, comparing fatal accidents (underground mines) rate per 100,000 employees between Poland and US this factor is lower in Poland. Mean values for US and Poland are 22 and 17 respectively (Figure 1.9).

Figure 1.9. Fatality rate per 100,000 employees in Poland and USA between 2014 and 2022

In comparison, data from Spain, where in 2015 there were about 4,500 employees in underground mines, fatality rate per 100,000 workers was much higher than in US (5.5 times) (Sanmiquel et al., 2018). There can be observed that there are, in general, two main causes of fatalities in underground mines, i.e.: ground instability (rock fall, rockburst, tremors) and powered machines (WUG, 2024; CDC 2025). In case of Poland and its type of underground mines this division can be disturbed due to black coal mining where is problem with methane and coal dust. In example in 2022 there was disastrous accident associated with methane and coal dust explosion with 16 casualties. Percentage of fatalities between 2021 and 2022 by accident class in underground mines in Poland and USA is presented in Figure 1.10.

Figure. 1.10. Percentage of casualties between 2021 and 2022 by accident class in underground mines in Poland and USA

Taking into consideration trend analysis between 2014 and 2022 (Figure 1.11) it can be concluded that tendency is stable, what leads to the conclusion that some new initiatives in many fields (technology, organisation, etc.) should start to decrease level of casualties in the near future.

Figure 1.11. Number of casualties in Poland and USA between 2014 and 2022 with trend lines

1.3. Monitoring and Prevention Methods – Advances and Limitations

1.3.1. Seismic Monitoring

The occurrence of threats in the form of seismic events is related to processes taking place internal structure of Earth. Disturbances in rock mass stability are influenced by both natural processes and processes induced by human activity. Seismic energy is emitted in the form of elastic waves propagation depending on the strength parameters of the medium, volume of rock masses and the state of stress. The seismic areas are monitored by seismic stations which enable the determination of the magnitude the event, location and vibration parameters. Seismic phenomena are monitored using specialized sensors (seismometers, geophones, accelerometers) which are used to record vibration parameters caused by earthquakes or other sources (Teisseyre et al., 1983, Marcak & Zuberek, 1994; Goszcz, 1999). The ability of tremors detection depends on the type of instruments, the availability of accurate timing, the location of the station relative to the earthquake site and the magnitude of the earthquake (Braile, 2009). Generally seismic tremors or earthquakes are monitored using seismometer sensors used to record ground movements. There is the Global Seismographic Network which is a digital network of seismological and geophysical sensors connected by a telecommunications network, serving for monitoring the Earth (Figure 1.12).

Figure 1.12. Locations of measurement stations within the Global Seismographic Network (Mooney & White, 2009)

1.3.2. Rock Stress Monitoring

State of the stress in the rock mass is a very important parameter in mining engineering. Knowledge about *in-situ* stresses, their value and distribution in the underground mine helps to control rock mass stability to ensure safe working conditions. Knowing the location of the stress concentration zones enables to carry out some remedial activities to lessen geomechanical hazards. Rock mass has a certain strength and, in a case, when stress concentration exceeds this value instability in different form e.g. rock fall, rockburst, subsidence etc. (Sazid et al., 2023; Gama, 2020) In general view, stability problems related to the stress level rise with depth, however, should be kept in mind that this kind of pitfalls can also be present in smaller depths. Thus *in-situ* stresses are crucial decision-making parameter in underground engineering activity starting from designing process, through exploitation, ending reclamation. This parameter, its distribution and magnitude has influence on the geometry of workings, their orientation and development sequence (McQueen, 2004; Amadei & Stephansson, 2012; Sazid et al., 2023).

There are two main sources of stresses in the rock mass: natural and induced. Natural *in-situ* stresses exist in the intact rock mass before any external influences and they come from gravity force and geological processes. Induced stresses derive from any mining activity which disturbs natural stress state in the rock mass. Types of rock stresses according to Amadei & Stephansson (2012) are presented in Figure 1.13.

Figure 1.13. Types of rock stresses

Looking into stress measurement two main categories can be seen, namely: indirect and direct methods. First group of methods are based on rock observation without significant impact on measuring method, in turn second group (direct methods) are covered methods that disturb rock conditions *in-situ* (Ljunggren et al., 2003). Classification of stress measurement methods is presented in Figure 1.14.

Figure 1.14. Classification of stress measurement methods (Sazid et al., 2023)

In-situ monitoring perspective indicates that group of methods that can be used are borehole overcoring methods, which use soft inclusion cells, deformation meters or solid cells. The principal of this method is based on the stress relief around drilled hole (Ljunggren, 2003). Stress monitoring system which employs soft inclusion cell uses soft and flexible material which is placed into borehole. Measurement of strain components of this material is used to calculate stress in surrounding rocks. It should be noted that this method allows to determine 3D state of stress from single point, hence more

measuring points can yield data to determine stress distribution for bigger area. Usage of deformation meters is similar to the soft inclusion cell, but this device measures diameter instead of strain. Nowadays measuring sensors in inclusion cell can use modern technology like vibrating wire (Zhang et al., 2013) and fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensors (Liang et al., 2022). Modern, available solutions allow to conduct long-term in-situ stress monitoring by means of hollow cells, which allow to determine stress changes over time. In modern mining data obtained from these kinds of devices can be successfully used to validate numerical models of rock mass making them more accurate and reliable. An example of this kind of tool is CSIRO HI-D Cell made by ES&S Australia (Figure 1.15).

Figure 1.15. Hollow inclusion cell (<https://www.geosystems.com.au/product/csiro-hollow-inclusion-cell-rock-stress-sensor/>)

Overcoring methods are applicable in long range and measuring depth can reach even 1000 m, however drilling equipment is needed, in some cases very sophisticated (long holes). Nevertheless, at smaller scale hollow cells are very useful and can deliver meaningful and reliable data which helps to provide data-driven mining operations. An examples of stress monitoring carried out by means of inclusion cells different types can be found in McQueen (2004), Ask et al. (2009), and Yin et al. (2015).

1.3.3. Displacement Monitoring

Displacement is both important and one of the easiest parameters than can be measured in underground mines, therefore is the most common monitoring parameter for most geotechnical control systems. In case of underground workings control of roof and sidewalls stability is crucial aspect to ensure safety for the mining crew and equipment. In most cases there are many symptoms manifested by rockmass during process of losing stability i.e. convergence, ground support damage, cracking, spalling, etc. (Szwedzicki, 2003). Thus, measuring of displacement has significant role in the process of ground control. It should be noted that deformation size can be very small and hereof hard to observe, hence resolution of the measurement system has to be appropriate. Due to hazard of rock stability, which is mainly focused on the roof strata, in most cases measurement of roof strata displacement or separation is applied, however movement of the rock mass can also be measured as deformation of the workings dimensions i.e. convergence (Jena et al., 2016; Fuławka et al., 2018; Walentek, 2019; Małkowski et al., 2020). An example template of workings monitoring that can be employed in underground mine can be seen in Figure 1.16 (Gong et al., 2019).

Figure 1.16. An example of displacement instrumentation in underground workings (Gong et al., 2019)

Extensometers

Extensometer is device that can measure displacement along one axis between two or more points. This kind of tool is typically applied in the borehole drilled in the roof strata. Length of extensometer can be reach even 300 m (extra-deep multiple-point borehole extensometer) (Xia et al., 2018), however in most cases this kind of tool is employed measure displacement in the immediate roof strata and has a length up to 10 m. Data yielded by devices which show growing of deformation in time suggests that process of weakening proceeds, value of displacement and its dynamics can be indicator of roof failure in the near future. Principle of extensometer operation is presented in Figure 1.17.

Figure 1.17. Principle of extensometer operation

The most popular type of extensometers are multi-point extensometers. Depending on the construction and type of employed sensors multi-point extensometers can be mechanical, electric, sonic, magnetic or optical. In modern types of devices measurement resolution can reach 0.01 mm with real-time data transmission, however

in standard applications accuracy at the level of ± 1 mm is appropriate (Mandal et al., 2018; PMPTL, 2025).

Convergence measurement

The aim of convergence measurement is to obtain data about changes in the workings shape and dimensions like floor heave, roof subsidence, sidewall movement (Ariznavarreta-Fernández et al., 2016; Małkowski et al., 2020). Due to its simplicity is the most used method in underground mines and is based on the measurement of distance between two reference points that can be in different parts of monitored underground structure e.g. workings, chambers, shafts etc. Nowadays several types of convergence meters can be applied, principle of operation is similar in all cases. Different environmental conditions that can be met in underground mines force selection of suitable type of device that can be mechanical, optical (laser rangefinder), etc. Routinely, measuring points are permanently fixed to the structure: usually one on the floor and one on the roof (Fuławka et al., 2018, Gong et al., 2018). Currently, one of the most popular versions is easily accessible optical device, where the measurement is carried out by a laser rangefinder, nevertheless in case of dust condition other type of measurement unit has to be employed e.g. telescopic, wire etc. Inherent feature of modern instruments is possibility of data transfer in real-time manner by means of different technology and protocols e.g. wi-fi, Bluetooth, wired etc. Simplified scheme of a solution with laser sensor is shown in Figure 1.18.

Figure 1.18. Simplified scheme of laser convergence indicator

Measurement of working's dimensions changes can also be carried out using inclinometers and other devices for angle measurements (geodetic). Inclinometer systems are able to determine angles of different structures or elements like sidewalls, roof, floor, rockbolts etc. In most cases system consists of two main elements i.e. inclination sensor and recorder. Components of exemplary inclinometer system is presented in Figure 1.19 (Fuławka et al., 2018).

Communication terminal

Sensor

Figure 1.19. Elements of inclinometer system

System based on the angular encoders can be extended to creates more sophisticated structure. Ariznavarreta-Fernández et al. (2016) proposed system called CANG (Convergence by means of ANGular Sensors) where group of sensors can be placed at the structure and monitor angels and length between determined points creates an open polygon e.g. among perimeter of the tunnel (Figure 1.20).

Figure 1.20. Plan of CANG system

Besides from the convergence measurement methods mentioned before there is modern group of methods based on photogrammetry and laser scanning (Slaker et al., 2018). Development in laser scanning technology and photogrammetry allow to apply these technologies in underground conditions. Nevertheless, it seems that photogrammetry has important advantages over laser scanning, namely necessary device is cost-effective and data collection process is relatively simple and fast. Laser scanners are more expensive, need well trained personnel and time consumed. Research conducted in underground environment shows that photogrammetry measurements are feasible, reliable and reach millimetres accuracy. It's worth mentioning that instead of data regarding tunnel convergence this method allows to yield more valuable information like rock joint orientation and spacing, cracks, rock layers etc. (Benton et al., 2016; Benton et al., 2017). However, it seems that this method is applicable to close-range measurement and cannot be used in real-time monitoring due to devices and software constraints.

Laser technology is very popular in 3D scanning systems; hence this technology is also applied in underground mines (Ferrero et al., 2009). Fast development and miniaturisation of optical sensors allows simplified measurement operations which are based mainly on the light detection and ranging (LiDAR) principals. Therefore these systems are greatly applied in many applications including deformation monitoring (Jones & Beck, 2017; Rodriguez, 2017; Slaker et al., 2018; Kumar Singh et al., 2023). Current available laser technology allows to use accurate laser-derived cloud point data to monitor deformation in 3D environment by comparing scans carried out in suitable time manner. In results data regarding magnitude, direction and speed of changes is regularly available in quantitative form. This technology can be adopted to the needs and provides comprehensive data for different mining departments e.g. geology, geodesic, geomechanics. Looking from the geomechanical perspective application of laser scanning in mining process is presented in Figure 1.21 (Jones & Back, 2017).

Figure 1.21. Flowchart of using laser scanning in mines

There are mainly two methods employed to conduct laser scan in underground conditions i.e. terrestrial laser scanning (TLS) and mobile laser scanning (MLS). Both methods yield geospatial data that can be valuable for mining applications though there can be some demands which can prefer one of them in some cases. In general view TLS method is more accurate but due to its static form and time-consuming is more suitable for more accurate needs (millimetre level) and smaller-scale like convergence monitoring. In the light of large-scale projects MLS technology is more accurate due to its mobility. However rapid development of MLS and drone technologies which improve accuracy and mobility of the system seems to prefer MLS technology in mining application (Singh et al., 2023).

Geophysics methods

Underground geologic formations, their composition and structure can also be investigated by means of various geophysics methods. Moreover some of these methods may be employed for the evaluation of the rock mass parameters like rock quality designation (RQD), rock core index (RCI), rock mass integrity coefficient (Hasan

et al., 2022; Hasan et al., 2023). These methods provide data to describe, in qualitative and quantitative form, different rock mass parameters and features like (Day-Lewis et al., 2017; Joutsenvaara et al., 2025):

- structure and structural integrity (geometry, discontinuities, hardness),
- spatial density distribution,
- electromagnetic properties,
- mineral composition.

All this data helps to create high-resolution images of rock mass and model of the mineral resources from different perspective i.e. geologic, engineering, geomechanics etc. Main group of geophysical methods (DeParis et al., 2012) are listed in Table 1.7.

Table 1.7. Main geophysical measurement methods

Method	Measurement	Physical parameter
Seismic	propagation time	wave velocity
Electric	electric potential	electric resistivity
Gravimetric	gravitational acceleration	density
Magnetic	magnetic field	magnetic susceptibility
Electromagnetic	electromagnetic field	electric resistivity
Radar	propagation time	dielectric constant

Seismic methods

Within these methods the following ones can be distinguished: seismic reflection, seismic refraction, seismic tomography, ambient seismic noise measurements, spectral analysis and multi-channel analysis of surface waves, borehole seismic method, vertical seismic profiling (Kovačević et al., 2013). Seismic reflection and refraction methods measure amplitude and arrival time of seismic wave which is artificially generated. Simplified diagram which shows principle of both methods is presented in Figure 1.22. These methods are effectively employed to evaluate internal structure of orebody in large scale, especial at the recognition stages. According obtained data the following structure can be mapped: depth of bedrock, large faults, fracture zones, depth of water table etc. Depends on the given application and employed equipment, in fractured rocks, resolution of these methods is 1 – 10 m, lateral extension up to 1000 m and depth up to 500 m, nonetheless if there are demands of more detailed data borehole methods must be applied for better resolution. However, application of borehole methods is associated with higher cost and invasiveness (Day-Lewis et al., 2017).

Figure 1.22. Principal of reflected and refracted methods (Zainal Abidin et al., 2011)

Cooperation of more than one method can create some hybrid systems aimed to achieve better results (e.g. seismic reflection and refraction method). Seismic borehole methods are not commonly used due to complexity and cost.

Electric methods

Differences in electric parameters of rock layers and structures are also employed to the mapping of their underground building. It can be done by measuring of electrical resistivity and conducting electrical resistivity tomography (ERT). Reliable and accurate data depends on differences in resistivity between rocks it means that materials with slight differences cannot be precisely determined, however even in good conditions for ERT method, this kind of survey should be combined with data from other methods to properly interpret geological structures (Hasan et al., 2020). Figure 1.23 presents ranges of resistivity of some rocks.

Figure 1.23. Ranges of electrical resistivity for selected rocks (Kovačević et al., 2013)

Nowadays resistivity surveys are mostly carried out in 1D and 2D form. It is technically feasible to conduct measurement which provide data for 3D analysis, nonetheless due

to cost-effective perspective and data quality it is not normally applied (Kovačević et al., 2013).

Another method that can be included to the electric group is induced polarization (IP) which can limit ambiguity resulting from other method (e.g. ERT) (Revil et al., 2017). In general, rockmass can be treated as system resistor-capacitor which is used for recognition of rock strata and their structures. The principal of this method is similar to the charging and discharging of capacitor which is part of rockmass. During charging and discharging process, current and its characteristic is measured to determine chargeability of the analysed area of the rockmass. This electric parameter depends on the many factors like grain size, mineral type, presence of electrolytes in pores etc. IP measurements are often applied together with ERP survey, especial in the rockmass which is characterized by slightly differences in resistivity (Hasan et al., 2020).

Gravity method

The next geophysical method is related to gravity measurement to determine underground structures. This method uses Earth's natural gravity field and surveys some local anomalies which indicate alteration in local density cases by voids, rocks with different density, faults etc. (Vasiliević et al., 2014; Zongyu et al., 2024). Development of sensitive sensors allows to measure gravity field with high accuracy and yield reliable data for both 3D domain and time domain (Erkan, 2008). This method is also applicable to mining industry to research geological structure, orebody shape and boundaries, etc. (Madej, 2017). Determination of distribution of densities with proper resolution in some cases can be problematic due complex geology and access to the measuring points in 3D environment (Vasiliević, et al., 2014), however in case of mining application workings, shafts can be used (Vasiliević et al., 2014; Madej, 2017). General view of gravity alteration with depth increasing is shown in Figure 1.24.

Figure 1.24. Gravity alteration with depth increasing (Madej, 2017)

It should be noted that method is commonly used geophysical method, nonetheless, is not free from some drawbacks, improvement of resolution requires more measurement points, moreover abrupt density disturbances in close surroundings of measurement point have meaningful impact on measured data (Vasiliević et al., 2021). Interpretation of gravimetric data is also affected by uncertainty of solutions (Porzucek & Loj, 2021).

Magnetic and electromagnetic methods

Physical properties of materials that can be used as source of information are magnetic parameters. Magnetic features of materials are measured in Electromagnetic Profiling (EP) method, magnetic tomography (MT), magnetotelluric method (Adamo et al., 2020, Hasan et al., 2020). These methods can use natural magnetic field of Earth or artificially induced electromagnetic fields or. In first case anomalies in natural magnetic field are measured in second case artificially generated variable magnetic field generates current in conductive material which in turn creates secondary magnetic field which is measured (Joutsenvaara et al., 2025).

An example of magnetic method is magnetotelluric method called controlled-source audio-frequency magnetotelluric (CSAMT) which is in fact hybrid method that also utilised measuring of subsurface resistivity distribution. Basis of this method is complete electromagnetic theory described by Maxwell's equations. Capability of this type of measurement allowed to provide data from depth even more than 1000 m (Hasan et al., 2023). Electromagnetic surveys may be conducted by airborne tools like drones, which is very useful in difficult terrain both in time efficiency and large size of analysed area, nevertheless there are some limitations regarding resolution and depth of measurements (Joutsenvaara et al., 2025). In Figure 1.25 example of model prepared on the base of CSAMT survey is presented.

Figure 1.25. 2D resistivity picture from CSAMT survey (Hasan et al., 2023)

Radar method

Ground penetrating radar profiling (GPR) method is commonplace method applied in many investigations due to its simplicity, fast data transfer, good spatial resolution and low cost. Basis of this method is propagation of high frequency (from few tens of MHz up to several GHz) electromagnetic waves and their reflection. Waves are generated in form of pulses from the surface of ground penetrate soil and reflected from material with different properties and this signal is recorded (Adamo et al., 2020). It should be

noted that this method can also be applied in borehole (single-hole or crosshole). Principle of measurement is presented in Figure 1.26.

Figure 1.26. GPR operation principle

GPR measurement apart from its advantages also has some drawbacks (Day-Lewis et al., 2017; Adamo et al., 2020):

- high sensitivity to site condition e.g. clay or water content can attenuate signal very fast significantly reducing depth of surveying,
- difficult data interpretation,
- small range of depth, which in even favourable conditions reaches about 50 m only.

2. Applied Passive Technologies for Exploration and Monitoring in Underground Mines

Passive methods in underground mining play a key role in ensuring the safety and efficiency of deposit exploitation. Their main advantage is the ability to continuously monitor the state of the rock mass without interfering with the structure of the rocks or shaking them with artificially generated waves. By recording natural signals - mechanical, acoustic or from cosmic particles – it is possible to gain insight into the processes occurring on various time and spatial scales: from rapid events like microtremors, through slow stress changes, to long-term movements of rock masses. This information is essential for early warning of geomechanical hazards (rock bursts, collapses) and for optimizing exploitation plans and safety works.

Within recently developed passive monitoring methods, the most promising seems to be passive seismic and muography. Passive seismic records natural vibrations of the rock mass using geophones or accelerometers and allows for locating sources of stress and cracks; its effectiveness depends on the density of the sensor network and the sophistication of the data analysis algorithms. Muography – passive tomography using cosmic muons – uses the ability of these particles to penetrate hundreds of meters of rock, which allows for three-dimensional imaging of density anomalies such as voids or weakened zones.

2.1. Muography

Muography is an interdisciplinary field that leverages the unique properties of cosmic-ray muons for a diverse range of applications. It has evolved into an umbrella term (Tanaka et al., 2023) encompassing several distinct technologies and techniques. Each of these fields takes advantage of the key properties of cosmic-ray muons, including their strong penetration ability, relativistic velocities, and near-straight-line trajectories through matter.

Muon imaging, or muographic imagery, is the most established of these muographic methodologies, with a wide range of applications across industrial and scientific fields. In its broadest sense, muon imaging refers to the non-invasive imaging of large objects and subsurface structures. In this report, the term muography is used synonymously with muon imaging.

2.1.1. Fundamentals of Muon Imaging

Muon imaging, or muographic imagery, is a technique that exploits cosmic-ray muons to map density variations inside geological structures. Similar to X-ray imaging but on a vastly larger scale, this method enables the detection of density variations inside geological formations, industrial structures, and even archaeological sites—all without the need for artificial radiation sources. In mining industry applications, it allows for the detection of hidden cavities, dense ore bodies, fault zones, and other subsurface features without the need for invasive drilling or excavation.

Muons are produced when high-energy cosmic rays (mainly protons and heavy nuclei) interact with the Earth's atmosphere, generating showers of secondary particles, including pions and kaons. These particles decay into muons, which then travel toward the Earth's surface at relativistic speeds, meaning that they propagate near at the speed of light.

Key advantages of cosmic-ray muons in imaging include:

- **High penetration power** – Muons can traverse several kilometres of rock, unlike other charged particles that are quickly absorbed,
- **Near-straight trajectories** – Due to their high momentum, muons experience minimal scattering as they pass through geological materials, making them ideal for imaging applications,
- **Global availability** – The muon flux is nearly constant worldwide. This continuous flux of cosmic-ray muons provides a passive, universally accessible imaging source, eliminating the need for artificial emitters and enabling standardised measurements regardless of geographic location.

At sea level, the average muon flux is 150–200 muons per square metre per second, and the flux decreases logarithmically with increasing depth as muons are absorbed by overlying rock.

Muographic Imaging Methods

Since muographic imagery encompasses multiple approaches, it is useful to briefly outline them to provide a broader perspective. However, in AGEMERA, we specifically applied only absorption-based muon imaging (the first technique below). Muographic imagery primarily employs two main approaches:

1. Muon transmission imaging (absorption muography)

- Based on measuring the attenuation (in practice, “stopping”) of muons passing through an object,
- Denser regions block more muons, creating shadows that reveal internal structures,
- Effective for large-scale density mapping, such as imaging ore bodies, monitoring geomechanical changes, and detecting hidden cavities in mining operations.

2. Muon scattering imaging (scattering muography)

- Tracks the deflection angles of muons as they interact with different materials,
- More effective for detecting high-atomic-number materials, such as enriched uranium storage caskets,
- Provides 3D tomographic reconstructions of the objects of interest,
- Unlike absorption muography, which is effective for large-scale density variations, scattering muography is more suited for detecting smaller, high-Z materials inside a structure.

Muon radiography and muon tomography are both variations of muon imaging, but they differ in data acquisition and processing rather than in detector technology:

- **Muon radiography** produces 2D images from a single detector viewpoint. Data collected from these static measurements are typically visualised as polar plot images, showing the variation in muon flux across different angular directions,
- **Muon tomography (3D muon/muographic imaging)** is a more advanced form of muon radiography, where multiple detectors are positioned at different angles to generate a 3D density model of the target volume. Alternatively, a single detector can be moved across different underground locations, with repeated surveys taken from multiple viewpoints. The collected data are then combined using imaging algorithms to reconstruct the 3D density distribution from separate radiographic observations.

In short, the key difference between muon radiography and muon tomography is not technological (i.e., detector-related) but rather the ability to gather multiple perspectives by either using multiple detectors or moving a single detector to different observation points.

Muon tomography offers notably enhanced resolution and accuracy compared to single-viewpoint radiography. However, in many applications, resolution requirements may be lower, making muon radiography sufficient and eliminating the need for more complex tomography-based reconstructions.

2.1.2. Muography in Rock Engineering

Rock engineering encompasses the study and application of geological principles to civil and mining engineering, focusing on **underground stability, excavation safety, and—in the case of mining engineering—resource exploration**. The ability to image the subsurface noninvasively is critical for optimising excavation strategies, mitigating geomechanical hazards, and improving long-term monitoring of underground structures.

Muography, a passive, high-penetration imaging method, provides unique advantages in rock engineering by enabling direct density measurements of subsurface structures (Holma, 2023). It can be used to detect weak zones, monitor excavation-induced stress changes, map geological discontinuities, and identify remaining ore bodies in underground mines.

Muographic Applications in Rock Engineering

1. Geomechanical Hazard Assessment in Underground Mines

One of the primary challenges in deep mining is the prediction and monitoring of geomechanical hazards, including rockbursts, cave-ins, and pillar instability. Traditional methods such as seismic monitoring and borehole logging provide valuable information but are often limited by sparse spatial coverage or require costly drilling campaigns.

Muography provides a **continuous, large-scale imaging solution** that can:

- **Detect density anomalies** associated with fractured or deformed rock masses,

- **Monitor time-lapse changes** in rock density to assess stress redistribution due to mining-induced seismicity,
- **Identify weak zones** in rock structures before they become failure points.

For example, in **block caving operations**, muographic imaging can reveal **hanging wall collapses** and changes in the density of caved rock zones, allowing early interventions to prevent catastrophic failures.

2. Detection of Geological Discontinuities (Faults, Shear Zones, and Fissures)

Structural geological features such as faults, shear zones, and fractures can significantly affect the stability of underground excavations and ore body continuity.

Muography is particularly useful for:

- **Mapping fault zones** that may act as fluid pathways, increasing water ingress risks,
- **Identifying stress-related fractures** that could compromise underground stability,
- **Assessing geological heterogeneities** that affect excavation and mining planning.

A key advantage is that muographic detectors can be installed in underground tunnels or boreholes, providing a direct density contrast map of subsurface discontinuities without requiring invasive drilling.

Studies have demonstrated that density variations of as little as 2% at 150 m depth, 4% at 300 m, and 10% at 700 m can be detected using muography (Holma et al., 2022, and references therein). These sensitivity levels make it an effective tool for detecting faulted rock masses before they pose a risk to operations.

3. Monitoring of Rock Deformation and Subsidence

Mining-induced subsidence and **progressive deformation of rock masses** are significant concerns in underground operations. Unlike conventional deformation monitoring, which relies on **point-based measurements (e.g., extensometers, GPS, and borehole inclinometers)**, muography provides a **volumetric assessment** of density changes over time.

By deploying muon detectors at different locations underground, operators can:

- **Monitor stress redistribution** in rock pillars and excavated voids,
- **Assess density changes in backfilled stopes** to ensure stability,
- **Identify early warning signs of subsidence** before large-scale collapses occur.

A **4D muographic approach (time-lapse imaging)** can further enhance long-term monitoring by tracking density variations due to excavation, seismic events, and geomechanical responses.

4. Ore Body Imaging and Mineral Resource Management

Traditional exploration methods such as **drilling and conventional geophysical surveys** provide critical insights into ore body geometry, but they often lack the resolution or depth penetration required for deep mining. Muography offers an alternative high-resolution density imaging method that can:

- **Delineate ore bodies** by identifying high-density contrasts relative to surrounding host rock,
- **Detect remaining ore in stopes and mined-out areas**, optimising resource extraction,
- **Reduce exploration drilling costs** by identifying density anomalies before committing to costly borehole programs.

5. Infrastructure and Tunnel Engineering

Muography has also shown promise in **civil and mining infrastructure applications**, particularly for **tunnel construction, dam stability assessment, and underground facility monitoring**.

Key applications include:

- **Detection of unknown cavities** in tunnel excavation areas to prevent unexpected collapses,
- **Assessment of dam foundation integrity** by mapping density variations in bedrock,
- **Long-term monitoring of underground storage facilities** (e.g., nuclear waste repositories) to detect potential subsurface changes.

For example, muon detectors installed in **railway tunnels and subway excavations in France, Switzerland and China** (Nishiyama et al., 2019; Thompson et al., 2020; Mao et al., 2023) have successfully detected subsurface anomalies, improving excavation safety.

Future Prospects and Research Directions

The **commercial adoption of muography in rock engineering** is still in its early stages, but ongoing research is focused on:

- **Developing more efficient muon detectors** for borehole applications,
- **Enhancing data integration with seismic, gravimetric, and electromagnetic methods** to improve subsurface characterisation,
- **Applying machine learning techniques** to optimise muon data processing for faster and more accurate imaging.

As these aspects continue to improve an awareness of this method grows, muon imaging is expected to become a versatile tool for underground geomechanical monitoring, mining exploration, and large-scale civil engineering projects (e.g., Zhang et al., 2020; Holma et al., 2022).

2.2. Passive Seismic

Passive seismic methods do not require a controlled source, as they utilize the existing ambient seismic noise wavefield for monitoring and imaging subsurface structures. The main advantage of this approach is that seismic noise is ubiquitous in both time and space, meaning it is always present everywhere. This makes the method cost-efficient and non-destructive.

The primary technique used to extract useful signals from seismic noise is seismic interferometry (SI) - a rapidly evolving field of research that converts scattered wavefields into signals for seismic monitoring and imaging. Different types of SI exist, depending on the seismic source and wave type. Essentially, synchronously recorded seismic noise at two stations is correlated to extract the Empirical Green's Function (EGF), which represents the response that would be recorded at one station if a virtual source were located at the other. A key condition for this approach is that the seismic wavefield must be diffuse.

Since the noise wavefield exists continuously, EGFs can be determined repeatedly over time. By comparing EGFs from different time periods, structural changes in the propagation medium can be analysed. In particular, the comparison of coda waves—which travel longer through the perturbed medium—allows for the detection of very small structural variations.

To date, passive seismic monitoring has been applied to various structures, including geothermal fields, unstable slopes, groundwater reservoirs, mines, and dams. Monitoring structural changes using seismic noise can help mitigate risks, as seismic waves can detect internal changes before they manifest at the surface. This is particularly valuable in mining, where slope instability, subsidence, and potential mine collapses can be anticipated by observing systematic structural variations.

One of the main limitations of this method is the variability of the ambient seismic wavefield, which is influenced by fluctuations in seismic sources, such as seasonal climatic changes or variations in anthropogenic activity. These changes can imprint on the deterministic seismic responses used in SI. Additionally, external factors—such as soil saturation due to rainfall or air pressure fluctuations—can alter the shallow subsurface structure. However, various techniques exist to mitigate these limitations and improve the robustness of passive seismic monitoring.

3. Passive Determination of Rock Mass State Based on Muographic Measurements and 3D Numerical Simulations

One of the goals of task 4.5 of the AGEMERA Project is to test the possibility of passive (i.e., remote sensing) profiling of the deposit at great depths using muography methods in underground conditions. Particular attention was paid to the possibility of recognizing factors influencing geomechanical hazards. Therefore, the measurement campaign focused on the possibility of profiling discontinuities and fractures accompanying underground exploitation. Formation of fractures along with the advancing mining front contribute to the loosening of roof layers and increasing the local risk of collapse. At the same time, this process is accompanied by a decrease in the density of the rock medium. Therefore, it may be assumed that extend of fractures may be identified with muon imaging in favourable depth conditions and detector geometry arrangements. Knowledge about the range and speed of new cracks formation would undoubtedly be the basis for introducing constructive modifications in the mining operations aimed at increasing work safety and effective use of CRM.

Additionally, the possibility of passive imaging of static geologic structures such as faults was analysed. Determining the extent of the fault in a passive way would undoubtedly contribute to the possibility of constructive design of exploitation in this area, while increasing the efficiency and safety of exploitation.

Due to the pioneering nature of the research, the results of the muographic measurements were validated based on available geological knowledge, downhole measurements of convergence and stress, and the results of large-scale, 3-dimensional numerical simulations.

The research was conducted in two underground mining areas located in the Lubin underground copper ore mine, managed by KGHM Polska Miedź S.A.

3.1. Description of Trial Site – Legnica Głogów Copper Basin

Copper and silver are essential raw materials for the development of the global economy. During its 60-year history, KGHM has extracted over a billion tons of ore and produced 20 million tons of copper. Current resources allow for further work for about 40-50 years. Therefore, copper deposits located in the LGCB region can be considered as strategic for the EU economy. Unfortunately, mining progresses and exploitation are carried out at increasingly greater depths, which negatively affects work safety.

The LGCB region was selected as testing ground for the purposes of this study. The exploited area in LGCB region exceeds 500 km², and the depth of exploitation ranges from 600 to 1500 meters below the ground surface. Copper minerals occur in three main lithological varieties of rocks. The individual types of copper ores are sandstone, shale and carbonate. The four basic copper sulphides are most common in these ores: chalcocite, bornite, chalcopyrite and covellite. The deposit belongs to the stratoid type

of deposits occurring in sedimentary rocks with a varied thickness of up to several meters. The deposit series includes fault zones with throws reaching several dozen meters.

Excavation level is located at the boundary of Zechstein and Rotliegend and copper minerals are hosted by three main lithological rock types: sandstone, shale and dolomite (Figure 3.1).

Figure 3.1. Geological cross section of copper ore deposit in LGCB area

Strong dolomite strata with UCS up to 260 MPa is located in roof of workings, while floor consists weaker layers of sandstone characterised by UCS in range of 40-100 MPa. Deposit is excavated with room-and-pillar mining system with roof deflection. In systems of this type, the deposit is cut by means of perpendicular rooms, creating technological pillars that guarantee the stability of the roof layers. Then, in the second phase, the technological pillars are cut to the remnant/post critical size, which makes them yield and initiates the process of roof deflection (Figure 3.2).

Figure 3.2. Exemplary scheme of room and pillar mining system with roof deflection

As mining progresses, pillars in the area of roof deflection become plastic, allowing for slow inclination of the roof strata. At the same time, due to the high stiffness of the rocks, this deflection is accompanied by a process of cracking of the layers located above excavation level (Figure 3.3). As a result, roof in the liquidation area is characterized by

lower stability and tends to roof falls. Based on 60 years of experience, it can be stated that this method of liquidation of workings is safe and effective from the point of view of mining economics.

Figure 3.3. Cracking process of the layers located above excavation level

The problem appears when the roof layers are so stiff that a series of micro-cracks do not occur immediately after cutting the deposit. In such case stress accumulation zone is created on the border of mining front and liquidation area. The accumulation of elastic energy in the rock mass increases until at some point the high-strength roof layers breaks, which is the direct cause of mining tremors.

A large exploitation area, constantly increasing depth of extraction, and very strong rocks located in the roof layers determine the tendency of the rock mass to generate mining-induced seismic activity. Figure 3.4 shows the location of tremors recorded in the LGCB area since 2014 with magnitudes ranging from 0.9 to 4.0.

Figure 3.4. Location of mining-induced seismic tremors in LGCB area in the years 2014-2024 (EPISODES Platform, 2024)

In LGCB seismic measurements are carried out in underground excavation (underground measurements) and at surface seismic stations (surface measurements). The main aim of underground observations in copper ore mines includes determining the coordinates of the earthquake focus (X, Y, Z) and its seismic energy. That system consists of an underground network of measurement points connected by a telecommunications network transmitting data to the Mine Geophysics Station located on the earth's surface. Location of measurement points are optimized depending on the exploitation front changes. Vibration sensors can be short-period seismometers, low-frequency geophones, accelerometers with appropriate parameters (natural vibration period, attenuation, sensitivity). Surface measurements in the LGCB mining areas are carried out based on a network consisting of several dozen measurement stations (Figure 3.5). The method of making of measurements, analysis and interpreting surface vibrations has been specified in the Mining Seismic Intensity Scale GSI-2004/18 for mining tremors in LGCB (Stolecki & Jaśkiewicz-Proć, 2021). Developed scale assured uniform procedures for seismic monitoring, interpretation of vibrations recorded at surface seismic stations, archiving of measurements and assessment of the intensity of the impact of mining tremors on buildings, as well as on people, in mining areas LGCB. The scale also formulates the basic principles for forecasting surface vibration parameters for mining tremors in the form of the "Instructions for conducting surface seismic measurements, interpreting results and assessing and forecasting seismic vibrations induced by mining tremors in LGCB based on the GSI-2004/18 scale".

Figure 3.5. Location of surface seismic stations in the LGCB area

Figures 3.6 and 3.7 show examples of seismic station which is used to monitor ground surface vibrations.

Figure 3.6. Seismic station located on basement of the building (<https://grss.gig.eu>)

Figure 3.7. Seismic station located in concrete well (Grzebyk et al., 2016)

The advantage of classic seismic networks is undoubtedly the accuracy and precision in determining vibrations on the ground surface, but this is related with high costs of individual stations. The high costs mean that the number of these stations is small and underestimated. The development directions of modern seismic station networks are going in the direction low-cost seismic sensors that are less accurate but can provide more measurement data.

More low-cost devices could also improve the accuracy of passive seismic profiling (passive seismic tomography). This method is based on recording natural or mining micro-vibrations by a network of geophones or accelerometers located in the excavations. Analysis of the arrival times and amplitudes of waves recorded from different directions allows to recreate a three-dimensional model of the distribution of seismic velocities in the rock mass, which correlates with its structure, fracture zones and stresses. This method is particularly valuable because it provides information on stress distribution and internal structure in large volumes of rocks, without the need to use explosives or vibrating machines. Its main advantage is the ability to monitor large areas continuously and relatively cheaply (when the measurement infrastructure is already installed), as well as providing directly interpretable structural models. However,

the need for a dense network of sensors to obtain good spatial resolution and advanced algorithms for processing large data sets can be a limitation. An innovative complementary technique is muon tomography - passive tomography using a natural flux of cosmic muons. These particles penetrate hundreds of meters of rocks, and their weakening or scattering depends on the density of the medium. Detectors placed around or in mine holes record muon hits, which allows for the reconstruction of 3D density distribution within the rock mass. This allows for the detection of large voids, loose zones or density anomalies inaccessible to seismic. Muonography requires longer data collection times and specialised equipment, but its ability to image deep and hard-to-reach structures is a breakthrough in geomechanical monitoring.

3.2. Preliminary numerical analysis of stress changes with progress of the mining front in room-and-pillar mining

The preliminary analysis of stress and displacement distribution was performed using the GeoStudio package, and more precisely, using the SIGMA/W program.

The SIGMA/W software is one of the key modules of the GeoStudio package developed by GeoSlope. It is an advanced numerical tool designed for the analysis of stress, strain and displacement in soil and rock media in a two-dimensional approach, with the possibility of taking into account the variability of parameters over time. The application is based on the finite element method (FEM) and allows for both linear-elastic and nonlinear plastic analysis using various constitutive models. In the case of geomechanical analyses in underground mining, SIGMA/W is widely used in assessing the stability of workings, designing support and modelling the impact of mining operations on the rock mass.

In the conducted study, SIGMA/W was used to analyse the distribution of stresses and displacements resulting from the ongoing exploitation in the room-pillar system, taking into account the variability over time (3D approach: two spatial dimensions + time). The analysis was carried out for two selected exploitation steps, reflecting the actual progress of work in the underground mine. The model was mapped based on actual geometric and geological data, divided into three key zones: intact rockmass, technological pillars and the liquidated zone (goafs). For each of the zones, appropriate mechanical properties were assigned based on the GSI (Geological Strength Index) scale, which allows for the estimation of strength parameters of the rock mass depending on its quality and degree of structural disturbance. The following values were assumed in the analysis: GSI = 90 for intact rocks, GSI = 80 for pillars and GSI = 30 for the goaf zone. These parameters were used within the framework of the generalized Hoek-Brown criterion (GHB), which is a recognized nonlinear strength model describing the behaviour of rock masses in real conditions.

Exact rock strength parameters used for calculation has been presented in Table 3.3. section 3.3.5.

The use of the GHB criterion in SIGMA/W allows for realistic mapping of the degree of rock mass disturbance with the progress of mining front. Thanks to this, the model shows much greater reliability than classical linear approaches. In order to represent the geometric changes related to the progress of mining, the model was performed in two-time stages (Figure 3.8).

Figure 3.8. First stage of analysis (left) and the second stage representing mining geometry after 10 months (right)

The geometry of the model was prepared based on the data from exploration drill holes (Figure 3.9)

Figure 3.9. Geometry of the subsequent rock stratum above and under deposit level

Analysis of the results showed clear changes in the distribution of both the stresses (Figure 3.10 and Figure 3.11) and displacements (Figure 3.12). The highest stress concentrations were observed in the border of the mining front and the backfilling area.

While the displacements were most significant over the level of the backfilling area. One may observe that with the progress of mining and the creation of an extensive liquidated zone, the model showed significant changes in the stress structure: relief zones appeared in the vicinity of the goafs and new areas of stress concentration in the roof – especially at the boundary between the intact rock and the liquidated zone. The observed displacements became more dispersed and covered a larger volume of the rock mass, which can lead to the formation of fracture zones and micro-ruptures in the roof layers.

Figure 3.10. Distribution of total stress in Z direction for the first stage of analysis (left) and after 10 months of underground excavation (right)

Figure 3.11. Distribution of Max. Shear Stress for the first stage of analysis (left) and after 10 months of underground excavation (right)

Figure 3.12. Distribution of displacements for the first stage of analysis (left) and after 10 months of underground excavation (right)

The results of the simulation clearly indicate that the progressing mining has a significant impact on the dynamic changes in the distribution of stresses and deformations in the rock mass, especially in the area of the goafs. The stress zone moves with the work front, and its geometry and intensity change, which leads to a reformulation of the internal force system in the rock mass. As a result, it can be expected that stress and strain changes are also associated with local density changes of the roof rocks, which is a phenomenon particularly important from the point of view of passive methods based on density profiling, such as muon tomography. Density loss in excessively deformed areas can be one of the main criteria for detecting geomechanical hazard zones and should be taken into account in future correlation analyses.

3.3. Use case 1 - Geomechanical Risks

In the first use case, the muon imaging system was used to attempt to track the propagation of the fracture zone with the progressing exploitation and to identify zones of increased stress in the roof layers. The muographic measurements were carried out using two muon detectors to reduce the duration (i.e., total measurement time and improve resolution. Parallel to the muographic measurements, the following methods were employed:

- a series of convergence measurements,
- continuous measurement of seismic activity,
- passive seismic tomography,
- active seismic tomography.

The results of the measurements from the underground tunnel network were used to validate the results obtained using passive methods and to calibrate the numerical model that simulated the stress distribution along with the progressing exploitation (Figure 3.13).

Figure 3.13. Non-invasive rock mass profiling and modelling procedure supported by in-situ data collection

3.3.1. Description of Mining Panel

Geological conditions in the analysed area favour the occurrence of high-intensity seismic activity. In the direct roof of investigated area, strong dolomite layers with a thickness of over 30 meters and UCS reaching 160 MPa are present. Above, stiff strata of dolomite, limestone and anhydrite with a thickness of over 150 m are present. In turn, floor layers consist of strata of red sandstone with average strength (UCS up to 80 MPa) (Figure 3.14). Strong roof layers with the simultaneous presence of medium-strength layers in the floor generate conditions which favors the rapid softening and yielding of the floor and pillars what often lead to accumulation of elastic energy above the mining area and seismic activity occurrence.

Figure 3.14. Geologic profiles in G-2 mining panel

The analysed mining panel was excavated using a room-and-pillar system with roof deflection. In the first phase of exploitation (the first 6 months of measurement) the cut progressed from left to right, then the exploitation front was reversed by 90 degrees and the cut progressed from bottom to top (Figure 3.15). The reversal of the exploitation front was related to the regulations regarding rockburst risk management in the G-2 section.

Figure 3.15. Progress of mining works in the G-2 mining panel during the muographic measurement

3.3.2. Underground Data Collection

The muographic stations were located so that the measurement covered the area located above the progressing mining works. As can be seen in Figure 3.16 one station was directed against the advancing exploitation front. The second station was located on the side of the advancing mining works.

Figure 3.16. Location of muon detector in surrounding of G-2 mining panel

In parallel to the muon imaging, a number of measurement systems were installed in the analysed area. The conducted activities included convergence measurements, seismic measurements using the mine monitoring network, and active seismic

tomography using the innovative NEXGEN prototype measurement network, developed as part of the NEXGEN SIMS project co-financed by the Horizon 2020 program under grant agreement No. 101003591.

For the purposes of measurement of spatial displacement change over time a dozen standard mechanical convergometers were used with a reading frequency of once a day. With the progress of exploitation and the liquidation of the excavations by roof deflection, the location of the convergometers changed over time.

The location of the convergometers in the following months is shown in Figure 3.17. The colours of the convergometers labels correspond to their location in the following months.

Figure 3.17. Location of convergometers with respect to progress of mining works in G-2 mining panel

The measurements were carried out for a total period of 10 months. As it results from long-term measurements, the average convergence value in the area of the G-2 mining panel was relatively constant and amounted to about 100 mm/month (Figure 3.18).

Figure 3.18. Convergence measured in the G-2 mining panel with the average value for subsequent months

Seismic measurements were aimed at determining the parameters of seismic vibrations, localising the source and energy of the tremor and also used for passive seismic tomography. In the analysed period, there were 3 measurement stations in the vicinity of the G-2 mining panel. Each station was equipped with single-axis seismometers Willmore MK III, manufactured by Sensonics Ltd., Hertfordshire, UK. These types of devices are adjustable-period velocity-sensing tool adapted for in-situ applications. The recording rate of the Lubin mine seismic network was 500 Hz. The basic parameters of the Willmore MK III seismometers are presented in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1. Basic parameters of Willmore MK III seismometer

Parameter	Unit	Value
Bandwidth	Hz	0.1–150 Hz
Range of period adjustments	s	1–3
Temperature range	°C	-40 to +50
Movement range	mm	± 2
Dimensions	mm	230 × 135 × 115

More information on seismic monitoring in KGHM Polska Miedź S.A. mines can be found in the article by Fuławka et al. (2022).

At the same time, in the G-2 section, active seismic tomography was carried out in order to directly identify the seismic velocities and indirectly localise the zone of increased stresses. It was assumed that the increase in stresses in the rock mass would be a parameter correlating with the local increase in density, while on the other hand, the decrease in stress zones was associated with the development of cracks in the rock mass, which should in effect affect the decrease in rock density.

The monitoring system consisted of 14 triaxial accelerometers, 16 repeaters (amplifiers) and a recorder. The monitoring network was supplied with an independent power supply what allowed for continuous data acquisition, data transfer and data recording in case of the energy short cut in mains. The main components of the system were MEMS accelerometers fixed to the grouted rock bolts installed in the sidewalls surrounding G-2 mining panel. This method of installation ensured the efficient transfer of the seismic signal to the sensors and provided additional stabilization of the sensors.

During the measurements, a low noise, and low drift 3-axis MEMS accelerometers ADXL355BEZ manufactured by Analog Devices (Wilmington, USA), were used. The sensors record vibrations in three orthogonal directions and convert the analog signal into 20-bit digital. This type of sensor is characterized by long-term stability, low noise spectral density and low power consumption. Accelerometers were soldered to the printed circuit boards with a microcontroller and 16 GB of buffer memory and then placed in a hermetic case with a stainless-steel nut necessary to fasten it to the rock bolt (Figure 3.19).

Figure 3.19. Complete sensor unit (left) and sensor fixed to the rock bolt (right)

Each sensor after fixing to the rock bolt was connected to an individual repeater which was mainly aimed at amplification and regeneration of recorded signals from sensors and allow their time synchronization. The repeaters were equipped with 5 sockets: two for data transmission and power supply (input and output), one for the accelerometer plug and two sockets for external trigger sensors (Figure 3.20). Repeaters were connected in series and provided data transfer to the recorder.

Figure 3.20. Repeater

The technical specification of NEXGEN SIMS monitoring system was presented in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2. Basic parameters of NEXGEN SIMS system for autonomous seismic tomography

Number of sensors	14
Number of channels	42
Triggering mode	internal or external
Acceleration range	± 2 g
Power supply	5–24 V
Power consumption	max 0.6 A
Sampling rate	4,000 Hz
Frequency range	0–1,000 Hz

Figure 3.21 shows the location of the NEXGEN SIMS accelerometers in relation to the mining operations carried out in the G-2 mining panel.

Figure 3.21. Geometry of excavations with locations of sensors in the vicinity of the test site

As the system for autonomous profiling of the velocity of propagation of sine waves is a prototype solution, a series of in-situ validation measurements was carried out. As a result of a series of calibration shots, it was found that the system guarantees high repeatability of results under similar geological and mining conditions and with constant parameters of the vibration source (Figure 3.22).

The recordings collected with the NEXGEN SIMS system were used to:

- calibrate the numerical model by comparison of stress distribution within analysed area,
- to verify the possibility of using MEMS accelerometers to determine the rock state based on passive seismic and seismic noise analysis.

Figure 3.22. Results of pilot measurements using an autonomous system for measuring the velocity of seismic wave propagation

3.3.3. Preparation of Large-Scale Numerical Models

Numerical simulations were conducted using the 3D FEM-based GTS NX software, which is capable of performing large-scale non-linear analyses for the underground mining industry. The simulations were carried out under static conditions, employing stage analysis with a 1-month time step. The rock's behavioural properties were determined based on the type of structure. For example, sand and clay layers, along with dry backfill areas, were modelled using the Mohr-Coulomb model, while intact rock masses, technological pillars, residual pillars, and other rock layers were described using the Generalized Hoek-Brown (GH-B) criterion.

The GH-B model is an empirical failure criterion that determines the strength of rock in terms of major and minor principal stresses. It predicts strength envelopes that align well with laboratory triaxial test results for intact rock and observed failures in jointed rock masses. Figure 3.23 presents failure surface in principle stress plane according to GHB criterion.

Figure 3.23. Graphical representation of yield criterion (left) and failure surface in principle stress plane (right) for GHB criterion

The Generalized Hoek-Brown criterion is a non-linear model that relates the major and minor effective principal stresses according to the following equation (Hoek & Brown 2019):

$$\sigma_1 = (\sigma_3 + \sigma_{ci}) \left(\frac{\sigma_3}{\sigma_{ci}} m_b + s \right)^a \quad (3.1)$$

where σ_1 and σ_3 = major and minor effective principal stresses at failure; σ_{ci} = uniaxial compressive strength of the intact rock material; and m and s = material constants, where $s = 1$ for intact rock. Parameters m_b , s , and a are the rock mass material constants, given by equations 3.2-3.4:

$$m_b = m_i \exp \left(\frac{GSI - 100}{28 - 14D} \right) \quad (3.2)$$

$$s = \exp \left(\frac{GSI - 100}{9 - 3D} \right) \quad (3.3)$$

$$a = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{6} \left(e^{-GSI/15} - e^{-20/3} \right) \quad (3.4)$$

where GSI = Geological Strength Index; D = disturbance factor; m_i is a material constant for the intact rock.

In order to improve the calibration process, the calculations will also be performed in a linear system. For this purpose, in order to correlate the calculation results with the parameters determined in relation to the GSI scale, the parameters of the Deformation Module (E_{rm}), cohesion (c') and the angle of internal friction (ϕ') were calculated based on the following relationships:

$$\phi' = \sin^{-1} \left[\frac{6am_b(s+m_b\sigma'_{3n})^{a-1}}{2(1+a)(2+a)+6am_b(s+m_b\sigma'_{3n})^{a-1}} \right] \quad (3.5)$$

$$c' = \frac{\sigma_{ci}[(1+2a)s+(1-a)m_b\sigma'_{3n}](s+m_b\sigma'_{3n})^{a-1}}{(1+a)(2+a)\sqrt{1+(6am_b(s+m_b\sigma'_{3n})^{a-1})/(1+a)(2+a)}} \quad (3.6)$$

where: $\sigma_{3n} = \frac{\sigma'_{3max}}{\sigma_{ci}}$

$$E_{em} = E_i \left(0.02 + \frac{1 - \frac{D}{2}}{1 + e^{\left(\frac{60 + 15D - GSI}{11} \right)}} \right) \quad (3.7)$$

The discretisation of the model was based on a hybrid approach, i.e. a combination of hexahedron, pyramid and tetrahedral elements was used. Additionally, a gradation of the grid size was applied. Within the excavations, the grid had a maximum size of 2 m x 2 m, while within the surface layers the grid had a size of 30 m x 30 m. The model was prepared in a full-scale system, i.e. all strata were taken into account, starting from the floor of the excavations up to the ground surface. This solution minimises the uncertainty related to the inaccurate determination of the directions and values of the principal stresses. In the full-scale model, these stresses result directly from the model geometry and the effect of gravity. Ultimately, the model had a cubic capacity of 2.25 km³ (Figure 3.24).

Figure 3.24. Isometric view of the 3D model (left) with a zoom in on the direct surroundings of the mining area (right)

3.3.4. Displacement-based Calibration of Large-Scale Numerical Models

Parameter m_i was selected based on new edition of catalogues of physical and mechanical characteristics of deposit rocks in LGCB mine areas (KGHM, 2023). Parameters used for calculations in given scenarios are presented in Table 3.3.

Table 3.3. GSI parameters used during calculation of different scenarios

Type of structure	Intact rock mass	Technological pillars	Residual pillars	Backfilling
I scenario				
<i>GSI</i>	95	95	95	Sand (M-C criterion)
<i>m_i</i>	12.5	12.5	12.5	
<i>m_b</i>	10.45	10.45	10.45	
<i>s</i>	0.5738	0.5738	0.5738	
<i>D</i>	0	0	0	
<i>a</i>	0.5001	0.5001	0.5001	
<i>E_{rm}</i>	47,635	47 635	47 635	
<i>c</i>	5.19	5.19	5.19	
<i>φ</i>	44.7	44.7	44.7	
II scenario				
<i>GSI</i>	90	75	60	Sand (M-C criterion)
<i>m_i</i>	12.5	12.5	12.5	
<i>m_b</i>	8.7459	4.5056	1.8607	
<i>s</i>	0.3292	0.0483	0.0048	
<i>D</i>	0	0.25	0.50	
<i>a</i>	0.5002	0.5009	0.5028	
<i>E_{rm}</i>	46,588	32,249	13,213	
<i>c</i>	4.2434	2.54	1.6625	
<i>φ</i>	43.8	39.3	32.3	
III scenario				
<i>GSI</i>	80	60	40	Sand (M-C criterion)
<i>m_i</i>	12.5	12.5	12.5	
<i>m_b</i>	6.1193	2.4426	0.7179	
<i>s</i>	0.1084	0.0078	0.0003	
<i>D</i>	0	0.25	0.50	
<i>a</i>	0.5006	0.5028	0.5114	
<i>E_{rm}</i>	42,784	18,644	3737	
<i>c</i>	3.0685	1.8436	1.0927	
<i>φ</i>	41.5	34.5	24.7	

Based on 30 numerical simulations (3 scenarios × 10 monthly time intervals), it was determined which computational variant is closest to the convergence measurements recorded in situ. Ultimately, it was found that scenario 3 is the option closest to reality. Generally, the measurement curves almost coincide with the calculated curve within 1-7 months. Differences were observed in the last 3 months due to the lack of direct convergometers. It should be noted that the characteristics of convergence recorded in real conditions are close to linear and, in general, it can be stated that the vertical convergence of workings is in the range of 0.09-0.1 m per month. At the same time, the simulation results indicate the logarithmic nature of the roof deflection, i.e., in the first phase of excavation, convergence is at its highest level, but over time the deflection curve flattens, tending to a zero increase in convergence. This situation is most likely due to the limitations of the developed numerical models, which do not consider the plasticisation of the pillars over time. As a result, the model only takes into account displacements resulting from changes in the stress state near the excavated workings, while omitting the process of pillars yielding over time. The result of analysis has been presented in Figure 3.25.

Figure 3.25. Comparison of average measured convergence with results of numerical simulations

Taking into account the results presented in Figure 3.25, it was found that the model calibration led to a state in which the simulation results reflect reality to a satisfactory degree. A similar model calibration methodology will be used for use case 2.

3.3.5. Results of In-situ Measurements and Numerical Simulations

From the point of view of the AGEMERA project assumptions, the prepared numerical models should make it possible to determine the location of overstressed areas. The area of stress change over time will be correlated with the density measurement results from muon imaging. However, to make the results clear, both for mining operators and entities not specialised in geomechanics, instead of direct stress analysis, a parameter called Safety Factor (SF) was used, which is also based on stresses and at the same time refers to the strength of a given element/structure. In general, any values of SF below 1.0 may indicate the risk of instability. An example result of numerical simulations with the SF distribution map is shown in Figure 3.26.

Unfortunately, large-scale spatial models are problematic from the point of view of the interpretation of results due to the large amount of spatial data. Effective analysis of results requires advanced knowledge of the processes occurring in the rock mass, thanks to which the researcher can determine which area of the model is to be analysed and to what extent. Since the applied approach to calibrating the model in 4D is an innovative solution, in order to confirm the correctness of the obtained simulation results, additional validation of the results was performed based on a comparative analysis with the results of active seismic tomography and the place of occurrence of mining tremors.

In the first phase, simulation results were compared with seismic activity caused by mining activities in G-2 mining panel. For this purpose, a detailed 3D analysis of the distribution of the safety factor in the roof layers was performed for the three months characterised by the highest total seismic energy, i.e., January, June and October.

Figure 3.26. Results of numerical simulations performed based on calibrated rock strength parameters

The results were compared with hypocentral location of mining tremors recorded in these particular months. Figure 3.27 shows the results of the analysis for January 2023. The analysis shows that the zone of stress concentration and reduced SF values is located in the area bordered on two sides by goaf zone. The vertical cross-section through the numerical model indicates the concentration of stresses in the roof layers made of strong dolomites and anhydrite located approximately 100-150 meters from the level of the workings. Also, the influence of the backfilling zone (goafs) on the nature of the stress state before the mining front may be clearly indicated. What is important is the fact that the location of mining tremors coincides with the stress zone determined using numerical models in both horizontal and vertical directions. As seen in the vertical cross-section (Figure 3.27-left), there is a region with low SF index values in the upper part of the model. This corresponds to a clay layer with low strength parameters. However, due to its shallow depth and the material's plasticity, such layers do not trigger seismic activity.

Figure 3.27. Horizontal (right) and vertical (left) A-A' cross-sections representing safety factor distribution with tremors locations – January 2023

Figure 3.28 shows the analysis results for June 2023. During this period, as mining continued, the stress zone shifted towards the extracted area. At the mining front, there was one high-energy tremor with energy greater than 10^6 J, along with several moderate tremors of lower energy. Overall, the calculated area of reduced SF closely corresponds to the locations of the tremors. In terms of vertical distribution, like in January, the dolomite and anhydrite layers were most vulnerable to instability. Additionally, a stress relaxation zone above the goafs can be seen, affecting the SF index distribution in that area.

Figure 3.28. Horizontal (right) and vertical (left) B-B' cross-sections representing safety factor distribution within analysed area with tremor locations – June 2023

In Figure 3.29, the simulation results for October 2023 can be found. By October, the extraction of the deposit in the analysed section was nearly complete. The advancement of the workings zone had an impact on the stress conditions above the workings level and along the mining front boundary. The left part of Figure 3.29 clearly illustrates the development of an instability zone above the goafs. Similar to the January and June

analyses, the identified zone of increased stress aligns well with the locations of seismic events recorded in the G-2 mining panel in October 2023.

Figure 3.29. Horizontal (right) and vertical (left) C-C' cross-sections representing safety factor distribution within the analysed area with location of tremors – October 2023

Additional calibration of the results was performed based on a qualitative comparison of the zone of increased stress and the areas of increased seismic activity. A comparison of the FEM numerical simulation results with those obtained from the innovative system for continuous active seismic velocity profiling reveals a strong correlation between these two sets of results. As shown in Figure 3.30, right section of the analysed mining panel exhibits a clearly defined zone of increased seismic wave velocities. This zone lies between the intact rock mass and the backfilling area (dashed area). Similar results were obtained from the numerical simulations (Figure 3.30-left), indicating that the FEM non-linear model provides a good geometric representation of actual conditions, leading to a stress distribution that closely resembles in-situ status.

Figure 3.30. Comparison of seismic velocity distribution (right) with von Mises stress obtained with numerical simulations (left)

Taking into account the very complex analysis and multi-parametric approach, it can be stated that a well-calibrated model reflects the geomechanical conditions prevailing in-

situ and their change over time. At the same time, it was found that it is a good tool for qualitative comparative validation of muographic measurement results. As it results from the analysis, the progress of mining clearly affects the change in the range of the stress zone both in the area above the goafs and in the intact rock zone intended for further exploitation. With the progress of mining works, the stress values change, which should also be related to the density change. In the roof zone above the goafs, progressive disintegration of rocks occurs, due to which the stress accumulation zone is effectively dispersed. The fracture zone is undoubtedly also a zone of reduced density. In turn, in the area located on the between mining front and the solid rock, a kind of lever is created which generates a local increase in stresses and can potentially generate an increase in density.

3.3.6. Application of Muon Imaging to Assess Geomechanical Hazards in the G-2 Section of Lubin Mine

For the first stage of the pilot measurements, two sites were selected within the Lubin mine. As the mine is operational, flat concrete foundations and protective steel-net cages were prepared at the installation locations to safeguard the measurement devices. While the setup of the detectors and the initiation of measurements was smooth, extreme humidity gradually infiltrated the plexiglass casings of the detectors, forcing their removal from the site. In response, a gas-tight, corrosion-resistant stainless steel (inox) casing was developed, enabling the MTL muon detector to commence consistent data collection. Although the data from the initial pilot measurements were usable, they were limited in duration. Consequently, the results presented below are based on the steady-run data, which have been verified for consistency within statistical uncertainties. Figure 3.31 shows the selected locations on the Lubin mine map, along with photographs of the second version of the MTL muon detectors, which were tilted at an angle of 20–30 degrees towards the region of interest.

Figure 3.31. Location of muon detectors in the Lubin underground copper mine

The results presented below are based on the steady data collection from a 7-layer MTL muon telescope detector. The deep underground muon flux resulted in a track rate of

1.4×10^{-3} muons per second, with around 15,000 muons recorded over a 4-month period. Events from radioactive background and, to a lesser extent, electronic noise were two orders of magnitude higher than the muon signals, making the multi-layered tracking system crucial for obtaining reliable measurements. Figure 3.32 illustrates the angular distribution of muon tracks in polar coordinates (showing a clear tilt) and the calculated muon flux, where the expected azimuthal symmetry is restored.

Figure 3.32. Measured number of muon tracks (left) and the calculated muon flux (right) in polar coordinates at the Lubin mine

The measured muon flux was converted into the density-length of the rock it traversed. This conversion relies on the initial muon spectrum, for which several models are available. While most models agree on fluxes at moderate depths, they show greater variations above 1000 meters of water equivalent (mwe). Figure 3.33 (left) shows the calculated density height (density-length multiplied by the cosine of the zenith angle, which reflects the expected ground level in a given direction) using the Reyna model. The corresponding average density map is shown in Figure 3.33 (right).

Figure 3.33. Density height (left) and average density of rocks (right) resulted from muon imaging

Figure 3.34 illustrates the correlation between the topographic rock length and the measured muographic density-length for each angular bin. The average density is represented by a line ($\rho = 2.3 \text{ g/cm}^3$), confirming the method and demonstrating the effectiveness of the MTL muon telescope across its entire sensitive cone.

Figure 3.34. Density scatter plot

3.3.7. Application of Passive Seismic in Deep Mine Conditions

To determine the possibility of applying passive seismics in deep mine conditions, data from an underground network based on MEMS technology and from a surface network also consisting of MEMS-based devices were used. This task is beyond the core scope of the AGEMERA project, and was performed by the CUPRUM, LITH and CSIC teams in their own budget. Nevertheless, it was considered that the results of the analysis may be interesting from the point of view of the AGEMERA project.

As it turned out, in underground conditions, using MEMS technology, the recorded data were too noisy (accelerometer noise, mine noise). As a result, correlation calculations did not bring the intended results.

Better results were obtained using the surface seismic network, but these data could not be used for comparative analysis within the G-2 mining panel of the Lubin mine.

Details regarding the passive seismic survey system are presented in the report D 3.3 - Demonstrator of passive seismic survey system prepared by CSIC and LITH.

3.3.8. Passive Measurement Results vs. Simulations - Interpretation of Research Results

As demonstrated by a series of numerical simulations and long-term underground spatial measurements, the exploitation of the deposit using the room-and-pillar system with roof deflection significantly affects the stress state within the rock mass, particularly in the roof layers. Peak stress changes were observed at distances of 100–200 metres, and this area was monitored using muon detectors.

While the original plan was to deploy muon tomography, the survey setup ultimately produced only muon radiographic data due to constraints in the detector locations. Improved communication and planning could potentially have mitigated some of these limitations. As a result, long-term continuous measurements of muon flux did not generate sufficient data to support full tomographic reconstruction or to effectively track density changes related to geochemical hazards at depths of 700–750 metres below ground level. Nevertheless, it is important to emphasise that this outcome does not reflect a fundamental limitation of muon flux measurements, muon radiography, or muon tomography for such applications. Rather, the findings suggest that the number and/or size of the detectors, as well as the duration of the measurements, were insufficient. These limitations could likely be addressed through improved monitoring setup design, such as optimising detector configurations and extending measurement times.

These findings are valuable for identifying the limitations of the technologies used. Building on this experience, further efforts were made to explore areas of application for muon imaging in the conditions of a deep underground mine. To this end, a mining panel located in a zone of intense tectonic disturbances (faults) was selected as Use Case 2. Identifying the locations of faults would allow for improved planning of exploitation, ultimately contributing to more effective and safer extraction of critical raw materials (CRMs).

3.4. Use case 2 - Identification of Caverns Filled with Water/Gas and Profiling of Tectonic Fault

Use case 2 measurements were planned based on the results and conclusions gathered from the measurements in use case 1. Since it is known that at great depths muographic measurement is not suitable for tracking time-varying phenomena, a mining panel in a fault zone with a high degree of water hazard was selected as a trial site. Variable density structures located in the roof of the excavations should be able to be effectively profiled using muographic measurement. Ultimately, the choice fell on the G-9 mining panel of the Lubin mine. The procedure for underground measurements, simulations and model calibration was similar to that in use case 1. However, passive seismics and seismic tomography measurements were ultimately abandoned. Calibration was based on convergence measurements (Figure 3.35).

Figure 3.35. Non-invasive rock mass profiling and modelling procedure supported by in-situ data collection

3.4.1. Description of Mining Panel

The G-9 mining panel of the Lubin mine is located at a depth of about 600 meters below the surface. This area includes numerous tectonic discontinuities in the form of faults of various lengths and different throws. (Figure 3.36).

Figure 3.36. Map of the exploitation excavations of the G9 mining panel along with the location of identified faults

Unfortunately, due to the lack of appropriate methods for non-invasive identification of tectonic discontinuities, the fault zone is not fully explored, which affects the efficiency and safety of the exploitation carried out in the G-9 mining panel. In the immediate vicinity of the G-9 mining panel there were 6 exploratory holes drilled from the ground surface to the level below the mining excavations. The location of individual holes in relation to the mining panel is shown in Figure 3.37.

Figure 3.37. Geometry of workings and location of exploration boreholes

Stratigraphic profiles of boreholes located in the surrounding of analysed mining panel are presented in figure 3.38.

Figure 3.38. Stratigraphic profiles in G-9 mining panel

The arrangement of geological layers is typical for the LGCB region. This means that mining is carried out on the border of sandstone and carbonates. The roof layers in this arrangement are characterized by high compressive strength reaching 180 MPa, while in the floor of the excavations the sandstone layers are characterized by a much lower strength varying in the range of 25-40 MPa (Figure 3.39).

Figure 3.39. Strength parameters of rocks in the analysed mining panel

Mining in this trial site is carried out using a room and pillar system with a roof deflection. Unfortunately, due to the presence of several fault zones, the cutting cannot be carried out in an even front. In order to minimise the geomechanical hazard, it is necessary to continuously adjust the mining system to the fault zone line, which should minimize the possibility of large-scale loss of stability in the fault area.

3.4.2. Underground Data Collection

Several mechanical convergometers were installed in the area of the operation. The frequency of data reading is once every 2-3 days. The location of the convergometers is shown in Figure 3.40.

Figure 3.40. Location of convergometers in G-9 mining panel used for model calibration

The spatial convergence measurement is carried out in continuous mode, however, for the purposes of calibrating the numerical model, data from the period January 2024 - September 2024 were used. As it results from long-term measurements, the average monthly convergence in the G-9 mining panel was between 30 and 70 mm (Figure 3.41). The measurement was divided into three 3-month time intervals corresponding to the steps in numerical simulations. The element subject to assessment was the convergence of workings in subsequent time periods and its correlation with the results of displacements observed on the roof-floor section in places corresponding to the locations of convergence measurements.

Figure 3.41. Results of long-term convergence measurement in G-9 mining panel

3.4.3. Preparation of Large-Scale Numerical Models

The calculations were conducted using GTS NX software, which is designed for advanced 3D nonlinear geotechnical modelling. The model was discretized using a hybrid approach that combined tetragonal, pyramidal, and hexahedral elements. This approach effectively represented the complex geometry of the mining panel while ensuring good mesh quality (Figure 3.42).

Figure 3.42. Isometric projection of a 3-dimensional large-scale empirical model of G-9 mining panel

The geology was taken directly from the boreholes, but the information on the faults is very limited. There is a lack of reliable information on the exact shape of the faults and their filling. To maximise the credibility of the model simulations, the faults were introduced into the model in accordance with the recommendations of the Lubin mine's geological department.

To enhance the accuracy of the analysis, the elements at the deposit level were categorized into different zones: backfilling zone, intact rock zone, large pillar zone (areas over 1600 m²), medium-sized pillar zone (areas between 120 m² and 1599 m²), and technological pillar zone (areas under 119 m²) (Figure 3.43). Each zone was assigned distinct strength parameters, and adjustments to these parameters did not lead to global changes in the results. Additionally, a series of tectonic faults with throws ranging from 15 to 25 meters were modelled above the deposit. These faults were filled with loose material (sand) to simulate a weak interface between the two layers.

Figure 3.43. Division of the numerical model into zones with different rock strengths

The approach to the selection of material models and reduction of rock strength parameters was similar to use case 1. The GHB criterion was applied, while the reduction of parameters was based on the GSI classification. The goaf area, similar to the fault filling, was modelled using the Mohr-Coulomb strength criterion. Sand was used as the filling material for these areas. This approach was intended to ensure the continuity of the model, while significantly reducing the strength of these areas.

3.4.4. Displacement-based Calibration of Large-Scale Numerical Models

The excavations are situated in sandstone layers of moderate strength. As a result, the laboratory strength test parameters for the sandstone were applied to the elements at the deposit level, including pillars and the intact rock mass. The liquidation zone is backfilled with dry material, so in the model, this zone is represented by loose material (sand), and the Coulomb-Mohr strength criterion is used. The input parameters for the sandstone at the excavation level are shown in Table 3.4.

Table 3.4. Parameters of intact rock mass at the excavation level

Parameter	UCS of Intact rock	Elastic modulus E_s	Cohesion c	Friction angle ϕ	Poisson ratio ν	Density ρ	mi
Unit	MPa	GPa	MPa	o	-	g/cm ³	-
Value	40,0	10.6	20.5	32	0.22	2.69	12

The model calibration involves adjusting the rock strength parameters by lowering the GSI parameter and increasing the D parameter. These adjustments were made individually for each zone at the deposit level. The specifics of the Hoek-Brown nonlinear parameters for the following calculation iterations are provided in Table 3.5.

Table 3.5. Calculation of non-linear parameter for GHB criteria

Non-linear parameters	Intact rock mass	Big Pillars (area over 1600 m ²)	Medium-size Pillars (area between 120 m ² and 1599 m ²)	Technological pillars (area under 119 m ²)	Roof deflection area
Scenario I					
<i>GSI</i>	100	90	80	70	M-C failure criterion
<i>m_b</i>	12	8.39	5.66	3.6489	
<i>s</i>	1.0	0.3291	0.1003	0.0281	
<i>D</i>	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.2	
<i>a</i>	0.5	0.5002	0.5006	0.5013	
Scenario II					
<i>GSI</i>	100	90	70	60	M-C failure criterion
<i>m_b</i>	12	8.24	3.65	2.24	
<i>s</i>	1.0	0.3168	0.0281	0.0072	
<i>D</i>	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.3	
<i>a</i>	0.5	0.5002	0.5014	0.5028	
Scenario III					
<i>GSI</i>	100	80	60	50	M-C failure criterion
<i>m_b</i>	12	5.66	2.2350	1.2876	
<i>s</i>	1.0	0.1004	0.0072	0.0016	
<i>D</i>	0.0	0.1	0.3	0.4	
<i>a</i>	0.5	0.5006	0.5028	0.5057	
Scenario IV					
<i>GSI</i>	100	70	50	40	M-C failure criterion
<i>m_b</i>	12	3.88	1.47	0.69	
<i>s</i>	1.0	0.0318	0.0021	0.0006	
<i>D</i>	0.0	0.1	0.3	0.5	
<i>a</i>	0.5	0.5014	0.5057	0.5114	

Satisfactory calibration results were obtained in the 4th scenario (Figure 3.44). Therefore, it was determined that the rock parameters reduced according to scenario IV will be used for further calculations of stress distribution in the roof strata. Generally, in the use case 2, the fault is located at the forefront of mining works. The assumption of numerical models is to verify whether exploitation near the fault affects the change of stresses in its vicinity, to assess whether this may have an impact on the results of the muographic measurement.

Figure 3.44. Matching the results of numerical simulations to underground measurements

3.4.5. Results of In-situ Measurements and Numerical Simulations

The aim of the numerical simulations was to determine whether mining operations conducted near the fault zone affect stress changes within the fault. The analysis used actual data on the progress of the mining front in the G-9 mining panel. The simulations represented the state in January 2024, May 2024 and September 2024. The simulations were performed based on calibrated rock strength data in accordance with the GSI classification. Figures 3.45-3.47 show a section of the model showing the distribution of the Safety Factor within the active mining exploitation area. The stage analysis made it possible to determine how the mining front affects the surroundings of the fault zone. The fault marked with a purple line in Figures 3.45-3.47 was subjected to analysis.

In January 2024, the mining front was approximately 50 meters away from the fault zone. An area of increased stress was observed in the roof of the workings on the border of the cutting area and the goafs. At the same time, it was noted that within the analysed fault (Purple line), the stresses were increased at the vertical contact of two adjacent layers, which results from the discontinuity present in the rock mass (Figure 3.45).

Figure 3.45. Results of numerical simulations - Safety factor distribution - January 2024

In May 2024, part of the mining front reached the analysed fault (Figure 3.46). As can be seen, the zone of increased stress above the cut zone has clearly widened, with the minimum values of the Safety Factor observed at the boundary of roof deflection zone and cut area. At the same time, it was observed that within the analysed fault, at the vertical contact of the layers, the stresses remained at a similar level as in January 2024. This may indicate that the change of stress state in the rock mass was too small to expose the fault and lead to its loss of stability.

Figure 3.46 Results of numerical simulations - Safety factor distribution - May 2024

In September 2024, the exploitation was carried out directly under the fault zone. Besides regular excavation, the roof deflection zone also reached the area of the analysed fault (purple line). As it results from the analysis, significant disturbance of the area under the fault and the yielding of the pillars lead to a significant decrease in the

determined SF at the contact of vertical layers, which may threaten the activation of the fault, i.e. loss of its stability.

Figure 3.47. Results of numerical simulations - Safety factor distribution - September 2024

As it results from the numerical simulations, mining exploitation does not have a significant effect on stresses in the fault area as long as the fault is not located above the area of ore cutting and roof deflection zone. Therefore, the muographic studies were planned to monitor the area undisturbed by mining exploitation, which will provide static and undisturbed conditions for long-term measurement. As a result, one detector was located below the fault zone marked in yellow in Figure 3.48.

Figure 3.48. Isometric projection of the numerical model with the highlighted fault being the subject of passive muon imaging measurement

3.4.6. Application of Muon Imaging to Identify Discontinuities and Water Hazard Zones in G-9 section of Lubin Mine

In the G-9 mining panel, a new-generation muon telescope was installed, specifically adapted to the challenging conditions prevailing in the underground Lubin mine. The position of the detector in relation to the fault zone is shown in Figure 3.49. The blue dashed line highlights the area of particular interest for this analysis.

Figure 3.49. Location of the muon telescope near the G-9 mining panel

Based on several months of continuous measurements, the average density of the overburden and the muon flux on the surface of single square meter in the area of the detector location were determined. The results of the analysis are presented in Figure 3.50.

Figure 3.50. Average density of rock mass (left) and muon flux (right) in G-9 mining panel

By analysing the results of muon imaging in relation to the geological conditions near the G-9 mining panel, it was found that, despite using only a single muon detector and

conducting measurements over a short period, it was possible to effectively observe areas of reduced density correlating with the locations of structural geological faults.

To the east of the detector, a series of smaller structural geological faults were identified, their presence effectively profiled through the analysis of muon flux. In contrast, to the south-east of the detector, there is a single, wide fault with a thrust of up to 20 metres. The average density map clearly indicates a reduction in density in this area.

Additionally, a significant area of reduced density was observed to the south-west of the analysed site (Figure 3.51). According to data provided by the KGHM geological department, this area does not correspond to tectonic discontinuities but may represent a zone of water-filled caverns, which contributes to a high level of water hazard in the G-9 mining panel and the continuous inflow of water into the workings.

Analysing the results of muon imaging and relating them to the geological situation in the vicinity of the G-9 mining panel, it was found that despite the use of only one measurement station and the implementation of measurements in a short period of time, it was possible to effectively observe areas of reduced density correlating with the localization of tectonic faults. To the east of the measurement station there is a series of smaller tectonic faults, the presence of which was effectively profiled based on the analysis of muon flux. In turn, to the south-east of the detector there is a single, wide fault with a throw of up to 20 meters. The average density map clearly indicates a decrease in density in this area. Additionally, an area of significant decrease in density was observed on the south-west side of analysed site (Figure 3.51). According to data provided by the KGHM geological department, this area is not an area of tectonic discontinuities, but it may be a zone of water-filled caverns, which results in a high level of water hazard in the G-9 mining panel and a continuous inflow of water to the workings.

Figure 3.51. Location of structural geological discontinuity zones (left) vs. muon imaging results (right)

In relation to the above, it was determined that muon imaging is an efficient method for detecting water hazard as well as geomechanical hazards associated with local presence of structural faults. This was confirmed through long-term, continuous in-situ muon flux measurements taken in the Lubin mine, 600 meters below ground level.

3.4.7. Importance of Accurately Determining Fault Parameters

As the usefulness of muon imaging for identifying fault zones was confirmed, attempts were made to qualitatively assess the impact of exploitation beneath the fault on the stability of the roof layers and the potential for inducing high-energy seismic tremors. The analysis was based on a series of numerical models utilising calibrated rock strength parameters (see Section 3.3.4).

Three different scenarios of mining under the fault were simulated:

- Scenario I: mining with front direction along the fault line,
- Scenario II: mining with front direction perpendicular to the fault line,
- Scenario III: regular mining front not adapted to the fault line.

The area of exploitation marked in Figure 3.52 was subjected to detailed analysis. The parameter assessed was the Safety Factor along the fault line at the moment when mining transitioned beneath the faulted area.

Figure 3.52. The area of the fault zone (yellow part) was subjected to detailed analysis

Numerical simulations show that mining along the fault line impacts the fault zone, particularly in the region between the mining front and the backfilling area. However, mining using the room-and-pillar system, as shown in Figure 3.53, should not result in a dynamic loss of stability for the fault or the pillars, as all areas in the model maintain a sufficient safety margin, with $SF > 1.5$.

Figure 3.53. SF distribution for mining with front direction along the fault line

When mining is conducted perpendicular to the fault line, a notable reduction in the Safety Factor is observed in the central part of the fault (Figure 3.54). Over the long term, this could lead to local collapses of the roof strata and, in extreme cases, may trigger the activation of the fault, potentially causing seismic tremors and rock bursts.

Figure 3.54. SF distribution for mining with front direction perpendicular to the fault line

It also appears unfavourable to conduct mining operations with a regular front line without considering the orientation of fault zones. Although it is generally assumed that a regular mining front reduces the likelihood of creating local areas of increased stress, thereby enhancing the safety of mining operations, this principle does not hold when mining beneath a tectonic fault. As demonstrated by the numerical analysis, when the mining front intersects the fault zone, a noticeable decrease in the Safety Factor occurs

within the fault zone, potentially leading to an increased geomechanical hazard (Figure 3.55).

Figure 3.55. Regular mining front not adapted to the fault line

Figures 3.56 and 3.57 provide a detailed comparative analysis of displacements and Safety Factor (SF) in the examined tectonic fault zone. The analysis shows that mining along the fault results in approximately 10% smaller vertical displacements within the fault zone. Additionally, the observed subsidence is distributed over a shorter distance, which is advantageous for stress distribution in the roof layers of the excavations.

In contrast, the mining scenarios outlined as II and III produce similar displacements within the fault zone. In extreme cases, the displacements generated by mining according to Scenario I were 33% smaller than those observed in Scenario II and 28% smaller than those in Scenario III. This pattern was particularly evident near the 390-metre mark of the fault.

The analysis of the Safety Factor distribution also yields noteworthy findings. In the case of mining according to Scenario I, the Safety Factor remains above 1.5 throughout the entire analysed length of the fault. In the other scenarios, the values are considerably lower: in Scenario II, 23% of the fault length has a stability index below 1.5 (with a minimum SF value of 1.36), while in Scenario III, over 21% of the fault length exhibits an SF below 1.5 (with a minimum SF value of 1.29).

△ Scenario I - Mining direction along the fault line ● Scenario II - Mining direction perpendicular to the fault line
 ■ Scenario III - Regular mining front not adapted to the fault line

Figure 3.56. Distribution of vertical displacements along the tectonic fault for the analysed scenarios

△ Scenario I - Mining direction along the fault line ● Scenario II - Mining direction perpendicular to the fault line
 ■ Scenario III - Regular mining front not adapted to the fault line

Figure 3.57. Distribution of Safety Factor along the tectonic fault for the analysed scenarios

4. Comparative Data Analysis with AGEMERA WebUI

Building on the workflows and AI Knowledge Packs (AIKPs) detailed in D4.3 and D4.4, 2D model cross-sections and 3D muon-derived density volumes for the Lubin mine have been published on the AGEMERA webUI. These visualizations demonstrate seamless integration of numerical simulations, geophysical inversion results, and voxel-based muographic data, all accessible via invitation-only project platform.

Figure 4.1. Multi lens tool look thought Safety factor data of G-9 for September

Figure 4.2. Shear stress for G-9

Figure 4.3. Distribution of seismic activity for G-2

A selection of horizontal cross-sections from the 3D geomechanical model, originally generated by KGHM/CUPRUM for the Lubin mine, have been exported as GeoTIFF slices and processed with the Raster AIKP for publication. Each slice is:

- Reprojected to WGS84,
- Dynamically stretched to enhance contrast,
- Converted to Cloud-Optimized GeoTIFF (COG),
- Published with accompanying GeoJSON metadata.

Within the [AGEMERA webUI](#), users can query “show me all in Poland like KGHM-CUPRUM” (Figure 4.1-4.12).

Published data include:

- G-9
 - Factor of Safety horizontal slices at -200, -100, -50, 5, 50, 100, 200, 300, 400, 500 m for January, May and September = calculated values for safety factor representing proneness of rock to failure. Safety factor $SF \geq 1.0$ stands for stable geomechanical conditions, while $SF \leq 1.0$ indicates instability,
 - Fault Analysis = distribution of Safety Factor in surrounding of analysed mining panel with special focus on near-fault area,
 - Displacement TZ = displacement within the numerical model in the vertical (Z) direction at the determined level,
 - Shear Stress = share stress calculated based of large-scale FEM simulations,

- Seismic Activity = distribution of seismic energy generated in analysed mining panel during the muon tomography measurement,
- Pressure,
- Working Stability = stability of pillars at the level of excavation.
- G-2
 - Factory of Safety 100 and 200 m above roof and at excavation level,
 - Passive Tomography Workings = map of seismic velocities within the rock mass determined based on passive tomography method with use of KGHM's underground seismic monitoring network,
 - Tomography = results of active seismic tomography with use of innovative 42-channel seismic monitoring system. The area of velocity profiling covers area of muon tomography measurement.

Data available in the system can be directly used by stakeholders like workers, citizens or entrepreneurs in relation to their needs. In case on citizens or business activity, data regarding seismic activity or subsidence can be interesting. Underground exploitation causes subsidence of surface and knowledge of their level can help to make some decisions regarding type of construction or other important issues. For example, potential stakeholders can see that extraction in G-9 mining panel caused maximum displacement level about 17 cm and this covers less than 0.1% of area only (Figure 4.4).

Figure 4.4. Displacement at the deposit level in G-9 mining panel

Seismic activity in G-2 mining panel can be seen in Figure 4.5. There can be observed that seismic events in this panel are focused on the central part of panel. This scope of data is also important to the mining engineers and helps them to manage exploitation process.

Figure 4.5. Seismic activity in G-2 mining panel

Data regarding geotechnical parameters of exploitation are important to the mining engineers to provide information on rock behaviour in analysed mining panel. This data is also important to workers engaged in exploitation process in this area which normally aren't involved in geomechanical aspect of exploitations. However, in some cases, their experience and access to this kind of data can bring important observations from the safety or mining operations point of view.

Another type of data that is useful, both for engineers and workers, are safety factors which indicate areas where instability of workings can occur. An example how safety factor looks at different levels of G-2 panel is presented in Figure 4.6. As can be observed in figure below, at deposit level, instability area is located in goaf area, what is in the line of assumptions, however at higher level situation looks different.

SAFETY FACTOR

Figure 4.6. Safety factor at different depth in G-2 mining panel

Very interesting data that is available in the system regarding passive and active tomography. Knowing the distribution of seismic wave velocity, which can be correlated with stress level in analysed area, provide additional very useful information regarding rockmass state. This data can be interrelated with other sources of data e.g. numerical simulation, seismic activity, measurement units etc. Figure 4.7 shows data obtained from passive and active tomography. This kind of data is very useful for geomechanical department and helps to control rockmass stability. In this case active tomography covered the operating area of mining panel only, therefore is smaller than data from passive tomography, however system that was applied in this issue was very innovative, cost-effective and provided good quality of data.

Distribution of seismic wave velocity

Figure 4.7. Data from active and passive tomography in G-2 mining panel

Easily accessible historical data regarding safety factor helps to follow changes in distribution of factor and allows to predict future behaviour of the rock mass. This information is very useful for mining engineers and workers from many points of view (geotechnical, safety, management). This kind of data that is available in opt-net system is presented in Figure 4.8., where distribution of safety factor in initial stage of exploitation in G-9 mining panel.

Figure 4.8. Safety factor in G-9 mining panel in January (deposit level)

On the base of data available in the system mining engineers can also see changes in SF distribution (Figure 4.9) where data from January, May and September are available. Similar data is available for several levels both below and above deposit level.

Figure 4.9. Safety factor in G-9 mining panel for three months (deposit level)

Another piece of valuable geotechnical data regarding G-9 mining level cover shear stresses which is shown in Figure 4.10. This mining panel is disturbed by a few faults where shear stresses were accumulated. This is very important information for geomechanical department to design exploitation in fault areas and select proper ground support.

Figure 4.10. Shear stress in G-9 mining panel

Results of simulation are able to analyse geomechanical situation from different points of view, e.g., Figure 4.11 shows analysis of faults behaviour in this area.

Figure 4.11. Safety factor in G-9 mining panel above deposit level

All underground activities use different types of workings in exploitation process, hence their stability is crucial both for safety and efficient production process. Therefore reliable analysis this matter using data from many sources i.e. seismic monitoring, convergence, local stress monitors (e.g. hollow cell, instrumented rockbolts) is required

both to control rockmass state and validate numerical models. Overall, all these steps create a continuous process of geotechnical analysis, what means that data from measurements updates models in continuous manner. In consequently obtained results are accurate and useful. Result of this kind analysis can also be seen in Figure 4.12. Information regarding workings stability is easily interpretable both for geomechanical engineers and workers.

Figure 4.12. Safety factor in G-9 mining panel at deposit level

Looking from the broader perspective there are many different groups of stockholders which are interested in access to the mining and geological data that have influence to their life starting from local residents, through entrepreneurs to national management level. Therefore there is real the odds of to improve communication between these groups. Some group of stockholders and their potential interest regarding mining and geology data can be seen in table 4.1.

Table 4.1. Importance of geological and selected mining data

Type of data	Importance			
	Local residents	Entrepreneurs	Mining management	Local / national government
Displacement	high	high	high	medium
Seismic activity	high	high	high	high
Workings stability	n/a	n/a	high	high
Seismic tomography	n/a	n/a	high	low
Shear stress	n/a	n/a	medium	low
Faults analysis	n/a	n/a	high	medium

5. Conclusions and Further Recommendations

The current economic situation and its rapid development highlight the necessity of implementing solutions aimed at the effective exploration and extraction of critical raw materials (CRM) within the European Union. Unfortunately, newly discovered deposits are often located in challenging geological and mining conditions, meaning their exploitation is accompanied by numerous risks that affect both the continuity and economics of extraction.

The solutions developed and tested within the AGEMERA project have the potential to deliver a breakthrough in CRM mining across the EU. The innovative methods and research results are particularly valuable as they have been tested under real deep-mine conditions. Consequently, the conclusions regarding the strengths and weaknesses of each analysed solution are supported by feedback from mining operators such as KGHM Polska Miedź S.A.

Below is a summary of the individual solutions for sustainable exploration and mining of CRM developed within the AGEMERA project.

5.1. Numerical Simulations

Numerical simulations are a highly effective tool, widely used in fields such as mechanical engineering, civil engineering, construction, and the space industry. Computer-based solutions also hold significant value for the mining sector. Analyses of the stability of geotechnical structures such as Tailing Storage Facilities (TSFs) and stability assessments of underground chambers have been discussed in the literature in recent years.

However, as the scale of a numerical model increases, its inconsistency tends to grow. This arises from the variable geomechanical properties of rocks and the presence of geological formations that were not fully characterised during the exploration phase. As a result, numerical simulations are not yet widely adopted as a design tool for large-scale mining operations.

This situation could change if effective methods for model calibration were developed, helping to improve the accuracy of hazard assessments and providing a reliable basis for the design of CRM mining operations.

Within the AGEMERA project, a four-dimensional model validation approach was proposed, based on underground convergence measurements, stress measurements, and seismic activity monitoring. Calibration involved the widely used GSI rock classification system and consisted of the gradual adjustment of rock strength parameters within the numerical model until appropriate convergence between the simulation results and in-situ measurements was achieved.

As a result, it was possible to achieve unprecedented accuracy in the numerical model, enabling the simulation results to be used not only for planning safe and effective CRM extraction at great depths but also for preliminary three-dimensional validation of new

methods of spatial rock mass profiling, such as passive seismic techniques and muon imaging.

The approach proposed by the KGHM CUPRUM team was tested on two mining panels that were extremely different in terms of geological and mining conditions. The first mining panel (G-2) was characterised by favourable geological conditions (no tectonic disturbances, no water hazard), which allowed exploitation to proceed without major disruptions and at a steady pace over the following months. Numerical simulations enabled the assessment of the impact of mining front progression on the stress state surrounding the excavations and on the seismic hazard level in the G-2 panel of the Lubin mine. In addition, the mining panel numerical simulations were used as a tool for the spatial validation of muon imaging results.

The second mining panel (G-9) was located in an area of intense tectonic disturbance with a high degree of water hazard. In this case, numerical simulations were applied to assess the impact of mining operations on the stability of fault zones and to evaluate the potential influence of mining activity on the results of muon imaging.

Ultimately, all activities related to numerical modelling within the AGEMERA project confirmed the value of numerical simulations in enhancing the safety and efficiency of CRM operations. Moreover, the developed model calibration methodology enables the preparation of numerical models of unprecedented scale.

5.2. Passive Seismic

On the Mining Panel G-2 of the Lubin mine, just before the AGEMERA project began, a prototype continuous active seismic tomography system was installed. The system was developed as part of the NEXGEN SIMS project co-financed by the Horizon 2020 program under grant agreement No. 101003591. The system included as many as 42 accelerometers in the area of the analysed field. Since the system collected data in a continuous mode, it was considered an ideal opportunity to verify the possibility of using data in the range of seismic noise to assess the applicability of passive seismic methods to assess the condition of the rock mass. In parallel, in cooperation with CSIC and LITH, a decision was made to simultaneously verify the possibility of using passive methods in the surface conditions of the KGHM Polska Miedź S.A. mine.

As it turned out, MEMS-based devices did not work well in underground conditions. The relatively high level of noise from the measuring devices and the noise from the technological processes determined the lack of the possibility of effective implementation of passive methods in underground conditions. The situation was completely different in surface conditions. In this case, passive measurements indicated certain relationships that could correlate with the processes of rock destruction as a result of mining operations, but research in this area should be expanded to include more measurement stations and be directly related to the current progress of the mining front.

Detailed results in this area are presented in deliverable D3.3. Demonstrator of passive seismic survey system prepared by CSIC and LITH.

5.3. Passive Muon Imaging

Muon imaging, which can be subdivided into **two-dimensional (2D) muon radiography** and **three-dimensional (3D) muon tomography**, holds great potential for application under deep mine conditions. The passive nature of the measurement, combined with the ability to collect 3D information using a single muon detector, ensures that the process does not interfere with the mine's technological operations while simultaneously enriching mine databases with valuable geological information on the overburden layers.

Within the AGEMERA project, muon imaging was employed both for passive geological exploration of the deposit and for assessing water-related and geomechanical hazards associated with underground CRM exploitation. Pilot measurements were conducted at two locations, corresponding to the sites used for numerical simulations: the G-2 and G-9 mining panels.

In the G-2 mining panel, the potential for tracking geomechanical hazards and the extent of the fracture zone within the roof layers above the area of ongoing mining exploitation was tested. During the measurements, it was necessary to dismantle and upgrade the muon detectors several times due to the harsh underground conditions (i.e., high temperatures, dustiness, near-100% humidity, and periodic high-intensity vibrations). However, MUON ultimately developed a device ideally suited to these challenging underground conditions and capable of collecting reliable data.

Based on several months of continuous measurements, it was concluded that the dynamics of crack development in the roof and the variability of the stress state in the rock mass during mining progress were too rapid to be effectively monitored using the deployed muon imaging setup at such a great depth. Although muon tomography could, in principle, be suitable for monitoring these processes, the constraints encountered during this study — including the limited number of survey locations, relatively small detector size, and insufficient measurement duration — prevented effective tracking of the rapid changes. Nevertheless, the method's capability for identifying static geological structures located in the roof of excavations, based on density contrasts, was successfully demonstrated through muon flux measurements.

In the next stage of the research, continuous measurements of muon flux were carried out in the G-9 mining panel, where static geological structures such as tectonic faults and aquifers in the roof layers posed significant risks to mining safety. Measurements in the G-9 panel were conducted from the outset using a modified muon detector, specifically adapted to the harsh underground conditions.

The analyses revealed that muon imaging — including simpler muon radiography — can serve as an effective tool for the passive identification of fault zones and areas with increased water content. As a result, data from muon imaging can be highly valuable for

regular mining operations, supporting more effective planning by incorporating the location of disturbed zones.

With knowledge of the position of fault zones and aquifers, it becomes possible to better control the direction of the mining front to minimise the risk of sudden fault instability. Moreover, information on the presence of unfavourable geological structures can be used to modify production blasting and distress blasting strategies, aiming to reduce the extent of the fracture zone in the excavation roof and, for example, minimise the risk of water ingress at the mining level.

5.4. OPT/NET GUI Platform

A key element from the point of view of data availability and analysis from various measurement systems, geological research and numerical simulations is the web-based GUI platform developed by OPT/NET company. A simple graphical comparison of the distribution of various parameters together with assigning the data an appropriate georeference undoubtedly facilitates the interpretation of results and identification of interdependencies between individual processes. The use of the OPT/NET application from the AGEMERA project allows, for example, tracking the state of stresses and displacements within mining excavations in the area of exploitation in relation to the ground surface. Data of this type are useful, among others, from the point of view of surface protection, because it would be possible to include in mining plans areas of surface infrastructure in which exploitation should be planned with caution. Considering that in many cases mining works are carried out under cities, bridges and expressways, information on the possible impacts on a given area updated in real-time would be the basis for conducting responsible mining.

References

1. Adamo, N., Al-Ansari, N., Sissakian, V., Laue, J., & Knutsson, S. (2020). Geophysical methods and their applications in dam safety monitoring. *Journal of Earth Sciences and Geotechnical Engineering*, 291–345. <https://doi.org/10.47260/jesge/1118>
2. Airborne hazard (2024). Airborne hazard management program. Government of Ontario. <https://www.ontario.ca/page/airborne-hazard-management-program> (Accessed 14.02.2025)
3. Ali, M. A. M., & Kim, J.-G. (2021). Selection mining methods via multiple criteria decision analysis using TOPSIS and modification of the UBC method. *Journal of Sustainable Mining*, 20(2), 49–55. <https://doi.org/10.46873/2300-3960.1054>
4. Amadei, B., Stephansson, O. (1997). *Rock stress and its measurement*. Springer Netherlands. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-011-5346-1>
5. Ariznavarreta-Fernández, F., González-Palacio, C., Menéndez-Díaz, A., Ordoñez, C. (2016). Measurement system with angular encoders for continuous monitoring of tunnel convergence. *Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology*, 56, 176–185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tust.2016.03.014>
6. Ask, D., Stephansson, O., Cornet, F. H., & Ask, M. V. S. (2009). Rock stress, rock stress measurements, and the integrated stress determination method(Isdm). *Rock Mechanics and Rock Engineering*, 42(4), 559–584. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00603-009-0058-9>
7. Atlas Copco (2007). https://miningandblasting.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2009/09/mining_methods_underground_mining.pdf (Accessed 20.01.2025)
8. Badri, A., Nadeau, S., Gbodossou, A. (2012). A mining project is a field of risks: A systematic and preliminary portrait of mining risks. *International Journal of Safety and Security Engineering*, 2(2), 145–166. <https://doi.org/10.2495/SAFE-V2-N2-145-166>
9. Baghaei Naeini, S. A., Badri, A. (2024). Identification and categorization of hazards in the mining industry: A systematic review of the literature. *International Review of Applied Sciences and Engineering*, 15(1), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1556/1848.2023.00621>
10. Benton, D. J., Chambers, A. J., Raffaldi, M. J., Finley, S. A., Powers, M. J. (2016). *Close-range photogrammetry in underground mining ground control* (P. E. Ardanuy & J. J. Puschell, Red.; s. 997707). <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2236691>
11. Benton, D., Seymour, J., Boltz, M. S., Raffaldi, M., Finely, S. (2017). *Photogrammetry in underground mining ground control—Lucky Friday mine case study*. 587–598. https://doi.org/10.36487/ACG_rep/1704_39_Benton
12. Bertrand, G., Cassard, D., Arvanitidis, N., Stanley, G. (2016). Map of critical raw material deposits in Europe. *Energy Procedia*, 97, 44–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2016.10.016>
13. Boyd R., Gautneb, H. (2016). Mineral resources in Norway: potential and strategic importance, 2016 update. Geological Survey of Norway, Report 2016.034
14. Braile, L. W. (2009). Seismic monitoring. W R. Young & L. Norby, *Geological Monitoring*. Geological Society of America. [https://doi.org/10.1130/2009.monitoring\(10\)](https://doi.org/10.1130/2009.monitoring(10))

15. Brake, R. (2015). Specification and Selection of handheld gas monitors (detectors) for underground mines. Proceedings of the 3rd Australian Mine Ventilation Conference, Sydney
16. Bukowski, P. (2015). Evaluation of water hazard in hard coal mines in changing conditions of functioning of mining industry in upper silesian coal basin – uscb(Poland). *Archives of Mining Sciences*, 60(2), 455–475. <https://doi.org/10.1515/amsc-2015-0030>
17. CDC (2024). National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH). Mining and Other Respiratory Hazards. <https://www.cdc.gov/niosh/mining/topics/respiratory-hazards.html> (Accessed 10.02.2025)
18. CDC (2025). <https://wwwn.cdc.gov/NIOSH-Mining/MMWC/Fatality/NumberAndRate?StartYear=2010&EndYear=2022&SelectedOperatorType=&SelectedMineType=1> (Accessed, 11.02.2025)
19. CDC Report (2012). Bugarski A.D., Janisko S.J., Cauda E.G., Noll J.D., Mischler S.E. Diesel Aerosols and Gases in Underground Mines: Guide to Exposure Assessment and Control. Report of investigations 9687. DEPARTMENT OF HEALTH AND HUMAN SERVICES, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health.
20. Code of practice (2016). Code of Practice, Ground or Strata Instability in Underground Mines and Tunnels. WorkSafe New Zealand.
21. Code of practice (2019). Department of Mines, Industry Regulation and Safety, Ground control for Western Australian mining operations – code of practice: Department of Mines, Industry Regulation and Safety, Western Australia
22. Day-Lewis, F. D., Slater, L. D., Robinson, J., Johnson, C. D., Terry, N., Werkema, D. (2017). An overview of geophysical technologies appropriate for characterization and monitoring at fractured-rock sites. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 204, 709–720. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2017.04.033>
23. Deparis, J., Jongmans, D., Garambois, S., Lévy, C., Baillet, L., & Meric, O. (2013). Geophysical detection and characterization of discontinuities in rock slopes. W S. Lambert & F. Nicot (Red.), *Rockfall Engineering* (1. wyd., s. 1–37). Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118601532.ch1>
24. Dino, G. A., Cavallo, A. (2022). Sustainable Raw Material supply: towards a more “domestic” approach, EGU General Assembly 2022, Vienna, Austria, 23–27 May 2022, EGU22-8747, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu22-8747>
25. EC (2018). European Commission: Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs, Bobba, S., Claudiu, P., Huygens, D., Alves Dias, P. et al., *Report on critical raw materials and the circular economy*, Publications Office, 2018, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2873/167813>
26. EC (2022). Eurostat, Accidents at work statistics. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Accidents_at_work_statistics#Analysis_by_activity (Accessed 23.01.2025)
27. EC (2024). European Commission, European Critical Raw Materials Act. https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_24_2748 (Accessed 17.01.2025)
28. Erkan, K. (2008). A comparative overview of geophysical methods. Report No. 488. Geodetic Science and Surveying. The Ohio State University

29. EU (2024). https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/sectors/raw-materials/areas-specific-interest/critical-raw-materials_en (Accessed 17.01.2024)
30. Eurogeologist (2022). https://eurogeologists.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/2022_EFG_List_Top10_Mining_Opportunities.pdf (Accessed 17.01.2024)
31. EuroGeoSurveys (2024). https://www.geologicalservice.eu/upload/content/1495/crm_map_a3_2024_small.pdf (Accessed 17.01.2025)
32. Euromines (2024). Raw Materials Mining in Europe Responsible, Necessary and Ready to deliver. Euromines Manifesto 2024-2030. <https://euromines.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/Euromines-Manifesto-2024-2029.pdf> (Accessed 21.01.2025)
33. Ferrero, A. M., Forlani, G., Roncella, R., & Voyat, H. I. (2009). Advanced geostructural survey methods applied to rock mass characterization. *Rock Mechanics and Rock Engineering*, 42(4), 631–665. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00603-008-0010-4>.
34. Frame. Frame—Forecasting and Assessing Europe’s Strategic Raw Materials Needs. Available online: <http://www.frame.ineg.pt/> (Accessed 20.01.2025)
35. Fulawka, K., Mertuszka, P., Solecki, L., Szumny, M., Kolodziej, R. (2024). *Identification of areas prone to seismic activity occurrence using 3d fem numerical simulations*. 311–320. <https://doi.org/10.5593/sgem2024/1.1/s03.41>
36. Fuławka, K., Mertuszka, P., Pytel, W. (2018). Monitoring of the stability of underground workings in Polish copper mines conditions. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 29, 00008. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/20182900008>
37. Gama, E. M. D. (2020). Suggestions, methods and examples of monitoring of rock structures and excavation of rock mass. *Geomaterials*, 10(04), 91–104. <https://doi.org/10.4236/gm.2020.104006>
38. Gamaletsos, P. N., Godelitsas, A., Filippidis, A., & Pontikes, Y. (2019). The rare earth elements potential of Greek bauxite active mines in the light of a sustainable REE demand. *Journal of Sustainable Metallurgy*, 5(1), 20–47. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40831-018-0192-2>
39. GeoERA (2024). Establishing the European Geological Surveys Research Area to Deliver a Geological Service for Europe. <https://geoera.eu/> (Accessed 21.01.2025)
40. Gong, H., Kizil, M. S., Chen, Z., Amanzadeh, M., Yang, B., Aminossadati, S. M. (2019). Advances in fibre optic based geotechnical monitoring systems for underground excavations. *International Journal of Mining Science and Technology*, 29(2), 229–238. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmst.2018.06.007>
41. Goszcz A. (1999). Elementy mechaniki skał oraz tąpnięcia w Polskich kopalniach węgla i miedzi [Elements of rock mechanics and rockburst in Polish coal and copper mines]. Biblioteka Szkoły Eksploatacji Podziemnej, Kraków 1999
42. Ground Control (2024). Ground control in underground mines. Government of Ontario. <https://www.ontario.ca/page/ground-control-underground-mines> (Accessed 10.02.2025)
43. Grzebyk W., Mertuszka P., Stolecki L. (2015). Rejestracje drgań rotacyjnych od wstrząsów górniczych w LGCB [Recordings of rotational vibrations from mining tremors in LGCB], *Wiadomości Górnicze*, no 2
44. Guideline for Inrush (2007). Guideline for Inrush Hazard Management. Mine Safety Operations Division, New South Wales Department of Primary Industries, MDG

1024. <https://www.resources.nsw.gov.au/sites/default/files/documents/mdg-1024.pdf> (Accessed 12.02.2025)
45. Hasan, M., Shang, Y., Meng, Q. (2023). Evaluation of rock mass units using a non-invasive geophysical approach. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), 14493. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-41570-y>
46. Hasan, M., Shang, Y., Yi, X., Shao, P., & He, M. (2023). Determination of rock mass integrity coefficient using a non-invasive geophysical approach. *Journal of Rock Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering*, 15(6), 1426–1440. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrmge.2022.07.008>
47. Iannacchione, A. T., Prosser, L. J., Esterhuizen, G. Bajpayee, T. S. (2007). Technique to Assess Hazards in Underground Stone Mines: the Roof Fall Risk Index (RFRI). <https://stacks.cdc.gov/view/cdc/9332>
48. Jena, S. K., Ritesh D, L., Manoj, P., Kuldip, P. (2016). Analysis of strata control monitoring in underground coal mine for apprehension of strata movement. *Proceedings of the Conference on Recent Advances in Rock Engineering (RARE 2016)*. Recent Advances in Rock Engineering (RARE 2016), Bengaluru, India. <https://doi.org/10.2991/rare-16.2016.81>
49. Jones, E., Beck, D. (2017). The use of three-dimensional laser scanning for deformation monitoring in underground mines. In *Proceedings of the 13th AusIMM Underground Operators Conference: Paper*, No. 066, 267-270
50. Jonsson, E., Törmänen, T., Keiding, J. K., Bjerkgård, T., Eilu, P., Pokki, J., Gautneb, H., Reginiussen, H., Rosa, D., Sadeghi, M., Sandstad, J. S., Stendal, H. (2023). Critical metals and minerals in the Nordic countries of Europe: Diversity of mineralization and green energy potential. *Geological Society, London, Special Publications*, 526(1), 95–152. <https://doi.org/10.1144/SP526-2022-55>
51. Joutsenvaara, J., Holma, M., Kuusiniemi, P., Kortenieniemi, J., Seivane, H., Marti-Linares, D., Schimmel, M., Casini, G., Buffett, G. G., Pirttijärvi, M., Saartenoja, A., Štimac Tumara, B., Kapustin, I. (2025). The horizon europe agemera project: Innovative non-invasive geophysical methodologies for mineral exploration. *Advances in Geosciences*, 65, 171–180. <https://doi.org/10.5194/adgeo-65-171-2025>
52. Kovačević, M.S., Marčić, D., & Gazdek, M. (2013). Application of geophysical investigations in underground engineering. *Tehnicki Vjesnik-technical Gazette*, 20, 1111-1117
53. Kumar Singh, S., Pratap Banerjee, B., Raval, S. (2023). A review of laser scanning for geological and geotechnical applications in underground mining. *International Journal of Mining Science and Technology*, 33(2), 133–154. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmst.2022.09.022>
54. Liang, M., Fang, X., Song, Y., Li, S., Chen, N., & Zhang, F. (2022). Research on three-dimensional stress monitoring method of surrounding rock based on fbg sensing technology. *Sensors*, 22(7), 2624. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22072624>
55. Ljunggren, C., Chang, Y., Janson, T., & Christiansson, R. (2003). An overview of rock stress measurement methods. *International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining Sciences*, 40(7–8), 975–989. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijrmms.2003.07.003>
56. Löow, J., Nygren, M. (2019). Initiatives for increased safety in the Swedish mining industry: Studying 30 years of improved accident rates. *Safety Science*, 117, 437–446. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2019.04.043>

57. Madej, J. (2017). Gravimetric surveys for assessing rock mass condition around a mine shaft. *Acta Geophysica*, 65(3), 465–479. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11600-017-0043-8>
58. Małkowski, P., Niedbalski, Z., Majcherczyk, T., Bednarek, Ł. (2020). Underground monitoring as the best way of roadways support design validation in a long time period. *Mining of Mineral Deposits*, 14(3), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.33271/mining14.03.001>
59. Mandal, P. K., Das, A. J., Kumar, N., Bhattacharjee, R., Tewari, S., & Kushwaha, A. (2018). Assessment of roof convergence during driving roadways in underground coal mines by continuous miner. *International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining Sciences*, 108, 169–178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijrmms.2018.06.001>
60. Marcak H., Zuberek W. M. (1994). Geofizyka górnicza [Mining Geophysics]. Śląskie Wydawnictwo Techniczne, Katowice 1994
61. McQueen, L.B. (2004). In situ rock stress and its effect in tunnels and deep excavations in Sydney. *Australian Geomechanics Journal*, 39(3). 43-57
62. Mijalkovski, S., Peltechki, D., Despodov, Z., Mirakovski, D., Adjiski, V., & Doneva, N. (2021). Methodology for underground mining method selection. *Mining Science*, 28. <https://doi.org/10.37190/msc212815>
63. Mining hazards (2024). Hazards in the mining sector. Government of Ontario. <https://www.ontario.ca/page/hazards-mining-sector#section-7> (Accessed, 10.02.2024)
64. Mooney, W. D., White, S. M. (2009). Recent developments in earthquake hazards studies. W S. Cloetingh & J. Negendank (Red.), *New Frontiers in Integrated Solid Earth Sciences* (s. 235–260). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-90-481-2737-5_6
65. Moore, K. R., Marquis, E., Shanks, K., Wall, F. (2024). Mining of primary raw materials as the critical foundation of ‘sustainable’ metals: A wicked problem for technology innovation clusters. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, 382(2284), 20230241. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2023.0241>
66. Moss, A., Kaiser, P. K. (2022). An operational approach to ground control in deep mines. *Journal of Rock Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering*, 14(1), 67–81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrmge.2021.05.008>
67. Mousavi, A., Sellers, E. (2019). Optimisation of production planning for an innovative hybrid underground mining method. *Resources Policy*, 62, 184–192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resourpol.2019.03.002>
68. MSHA (2024). The 5 Most Common Mining Fatalities – Probably Not What You’d Think. <https://mshau.com/the-5-most-common-mining-fatalities-probably-not-what-you-d-think/> (Accessed 17.02.2025)
69. Nieć, M., Galos, K., Szamałek, K. (2014). Main challenges of mineral resources policy of Poland. *Resources Policy*, 42, 93–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resourpol.2014.10.010>
70. Nieto, A. (2010). Key Deposit Indicators (KDI) and Key Mining Method Indicators (KMI) in Underground Mining Method Selection. Transactions of the Institution of Mining and Metallurgy, Section A: Mining Technology. 328. 381-396
71. NSW Code of practice (2015). Inundation and inrush hazard management. NSW CODE OF PRACTICE | WHS (MINES) LEGISLATION.

- <https://www.resources.nsw.gov.au/sites/default/files/documents/nsw-code-of-practice-inundation-and-inrush-hazard-management.pdf> (Accessed 11.02.2025)
72. Peng, S. S. (2015). Topical areas of research needs in ground control – A state of the art review on coal mine ground control. *International Journal of Mining Science and Technology*, 25(1), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmst.2014.12.006>
73. Pierce, M. E. (2019). Forecasting vulnerability of deep extraction level excavations to draw-induced cave loads. *Journal of Rock Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering*, 11(3), 527–534. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrmge.2018.07.006>
74. PMTPL, 2025. https://pmtpl.com/tell_tale_wire_extensometers_rotary.html (Accessed 12.02.2025)
75. Porzucek, S., Loj, M. (2021). Depth estimation problems in microgravity survey. *Acta Geophysica*, 69(2), 665–672. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11600-021-00553-1>
76. Pytel, W., Mertuszka, P., Fulawka, K., Szumny, M., & Stolecki, L. (2019). *Numerical modeling of rockmass behaviour due to blasting operations in underground mines*. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.1903.04815>
77. ReportLinker (2025). Reportlinker Research. <https://www.reportlinker.com/dataset/5b00284444d2db8abceb1998fbcae2a70eab7c6a> (Accessed 18.02.2025)
78. Revil, A., Murugesu, M., Prasad, M., Le Breton, M. (2017). Alteration of volcanic rocks: A new non-intrusive indicator based on induced polarization measurements. *Journal of Volcanology and Geothermal Research*, 341, 351–362. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvolgeores.2017.06.016>
79. Rodriguez, G. (2017). Underground versatile laser scanning solution. *Proceedings of the First International Conference on Underground Mining Technology*, 445–455. https://doi.org/10.36487/ACG_rep/1710_35_Rodriguez
80. Sakinala, V., Paul, P. S., & Fissha, Y. (2024). Promoting safety of underground machinery operators through participatory ergonomics and fuzzy model analysis to foster sustainable mining practices. *Scientific Reports*, 14(1), 16319. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-67375-1>
81. Sanmiquel, L., Bascompta, M., Rossell, J., Anticoi, H., & Guash, E. (2018). Analysis of occupational accidents in underground and surface mining in Spain using data-mining techniques. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15(3), 462. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15030462>
82. Sanmiquel, L., Rossell, J. M., Bascompta, M., Vintró, C., Yousefian, M. (2024). Data mining of accidents in Spanish underground mines in the period 2003–2021 caused by a collision with a moving object. *Heliyon*, 10(2), e24716. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e24716>
83. Sazid, M., Hussein, K., & Abudurman, K. (2023). Rock stress measurement methods in rock mechanics—A brief overview. *World Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 11(02), 252–272. <https://doi.org/10.4236/wjet.2023.112018>
84. Schoeman, Y. (2012). IMPLEMENTING AN EFFICIENT MINE WATER MONITORING AND MANAGEMENT PROGRAM : KEY CONSIDERATIONS. Conference: International Mine Water Conference, South Africa
85. Slaker, B. A., Murphy, M. M., Miller, T. (2018). Analysis of extensometer, photogrammetry and laser scanning monitoring techniques for measuring floor heave in an underground limestone mine. *Transactions*, 344(1), 31–37. <https://doi.org/10.19150/trans.8746>

86. Stolecki L., Jaśkiewicz-Proć I. (2021). Skala GSI-2004/18 – skuteczne narzędzie oceny wpływu wstrząsów sejsmicznych na zabudowę kubaturową i na ludzi w LGCB [GSI-2004/18 scale – an effective tool for assessing the impact of seismic tremors on buildings and people in LGCB]. *Czasopismo Naukowo-Techniczne Górnictwa Rud Miedzi „Cuprum”*, no 1-2, pp. 5-19
87. Szwedzicki, T. (2003). Rock mass behaviour prior to failure. *International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining Sciences*, 40(4), 573–584. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1365-1609\(03\)00023-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1365-1609(03)00023-6)
88. Teisseyre R. et al. (1983). Fizyka i ewolucja wnętrza ziemi [Physics and evolution of Earth's interior] Państwowe Wydawnictwo Naukowe, Warszawa 1983
89. Tomala, J., Urbaniec, M. (2024). Towards sustainable development in the European Union: A critical raw materials perspective. *Economics and Environment*, 88(1), 654. <https://doi.org/10.34659/eis.2024.88.1.654>
90. Tripathy, D. P., Ala, C. K. (2018). Identification of safety hazards in Indian underground coal mines. *Journal of Sustainable Mining*, 17(4), 175–183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsm.2018.07.005>
91. Umbach, F. (2024). <https://www.sustainablesupplychains.org/blog/unpopular-but-strategically-necessary-why-europe-needs-domestic-resource-extraction/> (Accessed 17.01.2025)
92. van As, A. (2021). Deep Mass Mining. The Key to Sustaining Mineral Demand into the Future. Sustainable Minerals Institute. The University of Queensland, Australia. <https://smi.uq.edu.au/files/88438/DMG%20White%20Paper%20Web%20ver.pdf>
93. Vasiljevic, I., Vuckovic, D., & Sretenovic, B. (2014). Underground gravity survey in a coal mine. *Podzemni Radovi*, 22(24), 21–33. <https://doi.org/10.5937/podrad1424021V>
94. Walentek, A. (2019). Analysis of the applicability of the convergence control method for gateroad design based on conducted underground investigations. *Archives of Mining Sciences*, 64(4), 765-783. <https://doi.org/10.24425/ams.2019.131065>
95. Water management (2024). Water management in mines. Government of Ontario. <https://www.ontario.ca/page/water-management-mines> (Accessed 11.02.2025)
96. Wittenberg, A., & De Oliveira, D. (2023). Critical raw material resource potentials in Europe. *RawMat 2023*, 24. <https://doi.org/10.3390/materproc2023015024>
97. Wozniakowski-Zehenter, M (2023). Identec Solutions, Miners Safety: Evaluation of Underground Safety Technologies. <https://www.identecsolutions.com/news/miners-safety-evaluation-of-underground-safety-technologies> (Accessed 17.02.2025)
98. Xia, K., Chen, C., Deng, Y., Xiao, G., Zheng, Y., Liu, X., Fu, H., Song, X., Chen, L. (2018). In situ monitoring and analysis of the mining-induced deep ground movement in a metal mine. *International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining Sciences*, 109, 32–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijrmms.2018.06.014>
99. Yin, H., Lefticariu, L., Wei, J., Guo, J., Li, Z., & Guan, Y. (2016). In situ dynamic monitoring of stress revolution with time and space under coal seam floor during longwall mining. *Environmental Earth Sciences*, 75(18), 1249. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12665-016-6071-x>
100. Zainal Abidin, M. H., Saad, R., Ahmad, F., Wijeyesekera, D., Tajul B., Tajul Baharuddin, M. F. (2011). Application of Geophysical Methods in Civil Engineering.

Conference: Malaysian Technical Universities International Conference on Engineering & Technology (MUiCET 2011)

101. Zhang, N., Zhang, N., Han, C., Qian, D., & Xue, F. (2014). Borehole stress monitoring analysis on advanced abutment pressure induced by Longwall Mining. *Arabian Journal of Geosciences*, 7(2), 457–463. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12517-013-0831-7>
102. Zhang, S. E., Bourdeau, J. E., Nwaila, G. T., Ghorbani, Y. (2023). Emerging criticality: Unravelling shifting dynamics of the EU's critical raw materials and their implications on Canada and South Africa. *Resources Policy*, 86, 104247. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resourpol.2023.104247>
103. Zongyu, Z., Peng, Y., Jiajun, Z., Linling, L., Xinyi, H., Zhenghao, S., & Zhongkun, Q. (2024). Application of microgravity measurements in urban underground space exploration. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2895(1), 012006. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2895/1/012006>

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